

Purbanchal University
Purbanchal University School of Engineering and
Technology
Biratnagar, Nepal

A Thesis Report on
Analysis of Data Mining Techniques Used For
Classification

In partial fulfillment of the requirements for the Degree of
Master of Science in Information System Engineering

Submitted By:

Pukar Karki

Registration Number : 010-3-3-11649-2018

Year/Semester: II/II

January, 2022

DECLARATION

I hereby declare that the work presented in this thesis has been done by myself, and has not been submitted elsewhere for the award of any degree. All sources of information have been specifically acknowledged by reference to the author(s) or institution(s).

Date: January, 2022

Signature:

Candidate's name: Pukar Karki

Registration Number: 010-3-3-11649-2018

RECOMMENDATION BY THE SUPERVISOR

This thesis entitled **Analysis of Data Mining Techniques Used for Classification** is prepared by **Pukar Karki** under my supervision and guidance for the partial fulfillment of requirement for the degree of **Masters of Science in Information Systems Engineering**. I hereby recommend this thesis for the final evaluation and approval by the thesis committee.

Er. Hemant Kumar Goit

Assistant Professor

January, 2022

LETTER OF APPROVAL

We certify that the thesis entitled **Analysis of Data Mining Techniques Used for Classification** submitted by **Pukar Karki (Registration Number: 010-3-3-11649-2018)** to Department of Computer and Electronics Engineering, Purbanchal University School of Engineering and Technology, Purbanchal University, in partial fulfillment of requirement for the degree of **Masters of Science in Information Systems Engineering** has been found satisfactory in scope and quality. Therefore, we accept this thesis as a part of the aforementioned degree.

.....

Thesis Supervisor

Er. Hemant Kumar Goit

Assistant Professor

Purbanchal University School of Engineering, Purbanchal University

.....

External Evaluator

Er. Sabin Kafley

Assistant Professor

Institute of Engineering, Purbanchal Campus, Dharan, Tribhuvan University

.....

Director

Er. Tejraj Giri

Assistant Professor

Purbanchal University School of Engineering, Purbanchal University

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

First and foremost, I would like to express my sincerest gratitude to Er. Hemant Kumar Goit, Assistant Professor, Purbanchal University School of Engineering, Purbanchal University for his invaluable guidance and counseling throughout the course of this thesis work. I would also like to extend my gratitude to the faculty members of Purbanchal University School of Engineering, Purbanchal University for providing me with the tremendous amount of direct and indirect counsel during the duration of thesis work. I would also like to convey my heartfelt regards to my friends and family for providing me with support and guidance. Lastly, I would like to express my profound thanks to the University of California Irvine for letting me and thousands of students like me to download the data from the machine learning repository free of cost.

ABSTRACT

Data Mining refers to the process of digging into the data so that one can find out patterns and gain knowledge about the patterns. Data is everywhere and it is generated in a sheer volume every day, resulting in the need to mine the data effectively. Classification is one of the techniques of data mining in which one finds a model that elucidates and distinguishes data classes and concepts. In this thesis, comparison of the different data mining techniques used in classification was done in Iris, Heart Disease, Wine, Car Evaluation, Adult, and Breast Cancer Wisconsin (Diagnostic) data sets. These data sets were unique and possessed a combination of varying characteristics like missing values, uni-variate/multivariate, having different nature/number of attribute etc. The natures of the aforementioned data sets were explored before their unique qualities were uncovered. Different data mining techniques for classification namely Decision Trees, K-Nearest Neighbor, Naive Bayes, Support Vector Machine and Artificial Neural Network were applied to each of these data set. Several performance analysis metrics like accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, confusion matrix and MCC were used to analyze the aforementioned data mining techniques and the runtime and space consumption was analyzed as well.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

DECLARATION	ii
RECOMMENDATION BY THE SUPERVISOR	iii
LETTER OF APPROVAL	iv
ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	v
ABSTRACT	vi
TABLE OF CONTENTS	vii
LIST OF TABLES	x
LIST OF FIGURES	xii
LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS	xv
IoT: Internet Of Things	xv
1. INTRODUCTION	1
1.1 STRUCTURE OF THE THESIS	2
1.2 BACKGROUND AND SIGNIFICANCE	3
1.3 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM	5
1.4 OBJECTIVES	6
1.5 CONTRIBUTIONS OF THE THESIS	6
2. LITERATURE REVIEW	7
2.1 OVERVIEW OF THE CLASSIFICATION TECHNIQUES TO BE COMPARED	7
2.2 REVIEW OF ANALYSIS OF CLASSIFICATION TECHNIQUE IN DATA MINING	10
2.3 MODEL ANALYSIS CRITERIA	12
3. METHODOLOGY	15
3.1 PROCEDURE	15
3.2 DATA INTRODUCTION	17
3.3 PRELIMINARY ANALYSIS OF DATA AND PREPROCESSING	17

3.3.1 ADULT DATA SET _____	17
3.3.2 BREAST CANCER DATA SET _____	21
3.3.3 CAR EVALUATION DATA SET _____	27
3.3.4 HEART DISEASE DATA SET _____	29
3.3.5 IRIS DATA SET _____	34
3.3.6 WINE DATA SET _____	36
4. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS _____	38
4.1 ANALYSIS ON ADULT DATA SET _____	38
4.1.1 Decision Trees (CART) Model on Adult Data Set _____	38
4.1.2 KNN Classifier Model on Adult Data Set _____	39
4.1.3 Naïve Bayesian Classifier Model on Adult Data Set _____	41
4.1.4 SVM Model on Adult Data Set _____	42
4.1.5 ANN (MLP Classifier) Model on Adult Data Set _____	43
4.2 ANALYSIS ON BREAST CANCER DATASET _____	44
4.2.1 Decision Trees (CART) Model on Breast Cancer Data Set _____	44
4.2.2 KNN Classifier Model on Breast Cancer Data Set _____	45
4.2.3 Naïve Bayesian Classifier Model on Breast Cancer Data Set _____	47
4.2.4 SVM Model on Breast Cancer Data Set _____	48
4.2.5 ANN (MLP Classifier) Model on Breast Cancer Data Set _____	49
4.3 ANALYSIS ON CAR EVALUATION DATA SET _____	50
4.3.1 Decision Trees (CART) Model on Car Evaluation Data Set _____	50
4.3.2 KNN Classifier Model on Car Evaluation Data Set _____	51
4.3.3 Naïve Bayesian Classifier Model on Car Evaluation Data Set _____	53
4.3.4 SVM Model on Car Evaluation Data Set _____	54
4.3.5 ANN (MLP Classifier) Model on Car Evaluation Data Set _____	55
4.4 ANALYSIS ON HEART DISEASE DATA SET _____	56
4.4.1 Decision Trees (CART) Model on Heart Disease Data Set _____	56
4.4.2 KNN Classifier Model on Heart Disease Data Set _____	57
4.4.3 Naïve Bayesian Classifier Model on Heart Disease Data Set _____	59
4.4.4 SVM Model on Heart Disease Data Set _____	60
4.4.5 ANN (MLP Classifier) Model on Heart Disease Data Set _____	61
4.5 ANALYSIS ON IRIS DATA SET _____	62
4.5.1 Decision Trees (CART) Model on Iris Data Set _____	62
4.5.2 KNN Classifier Model on Iris Data Set _____	63

4.5.3 Naïve Bayesian Classifier Model on Iris Data Set	65
4.5.4 SVM Model on Iris Data Set	66
4.5.5 ANN (MLP Classifier) Model on Iris Data Set	67
4.6 ANALYSIS ON WINE DATA SET	68
4.6.1 Decision Trees (CART) Model on Wine Data Set	68
4.6.2 KNN Classifier Model on Wine Data Set	69
4.6.3 Naïve Bayesian Classifier Model on Wine Data Set	71
4.6.4 SVM Model on Wine Data Set	72
4.6.5 ANN (MLP Classifier) Model on Wine Data Set	73
4.7 TRAINING TIME, PREDICTION TIME AND SPACE CONSUMPTION	74
4.8 SUMMARY OF THE RESULTS	76
4.8.1 Summary on the Adult Data Set	76
4.8.2 Summary on the Breast Cancer Data Set	77
4.8.3 Summary on the Car Evaluation Data Set	78
4.8.4 Summary on the Heart Disease Data Set	79
4.8.5 Summary on the Iris Data Set	80
4.8.6 Summary on the Wine Data Set	81
4.8.7 Summary of Training Time, Prediction Time and Space	82
5. CONCLUSION	84
6. FUTURE RECOMMENDATIONS AND LIMITATIONS	86
6.1 RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FUTURE WORK	86
6.2 LIMITATIONS	86
REFERENCES	87

LIST OF TABLES

Table 4.1 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of CART on Adult Data Set.....	39
Table 4.2 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of kNN on Adult Data Set	40
Table 4.3 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of Naïve Bayesian on Adult Data Set.....	41
Table 4.4 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of SVM on Adult Data Set	42
Table 4.5 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of MLP Classifier on Adult Data Set	43
Table 4.6 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of CART on Breast Cancer Data Set.....	44
Table 4.7 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of kNN on Breast Cancer Data Set	46
Table 4.8 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of NB on Breast Cancer Data Set	47
Table 4.9 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of SVM on Breast Cancer Data Set	48
Table 4.10 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of MLP on Breast Cancer Data Set.....	49
Table 4.11 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of CART on Breast Cancer Data Set.....	50
Table 4.12 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of kNN on Car Evaluation Data Set.....	52
Table 4.13 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of NB on Car Evaluation Data Set.....	53
Table 4.14 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of SVM on Car Evaluation Data Set.....	54
Table 4.15 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of MLP on Car Evaluation Data Set.....	55
Table 4.16 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of CART on Heart Disease Data Set.....	56
Table 4.17 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of kNN on Heart Disease Data Set.....	58
Table 4.18 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of NB on Heart Disease Data Set.....	59
Table 4.19 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of SVM on Heart Disease Data Set.....	60
Table 4.20 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of MLP on Heart Disease Data Set	61
Table 4.21 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of CART on Iris Data Set	62
Table 4.22 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of kNN on Iris Data Set.....	64
Table 4.23 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of NB on Iris Data Set.....	65
Table 4.24 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of SVM on Iris Data Set.....	66
Table 4.25 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of MLP on Iris Data Set.....	67
Table 4.26 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of CART on Wine Data Set	68
Table 4.27 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of kNN on Wine Data Set.....	70
Table 4.28 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of NB on Wine Data Set.....	71
Table 4.29 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of SVM on Wine Data Set.....	72
Table 4.30 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of MLP on Wine Data Set.....	73
Table 4.31 Training Time and Prediction Time for Various Techniques	74

Table 4.32 Space Consumption of Various Techniques.....	75
Table 5.1 Best Performing Classifier on Various Data Sets.....	84
Table 5.2 Advantages and Disadvantages of Different Techniques.	85

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1.1 The Data Mining Process	3
Figure 1.2 Model Construction and Test/Use	4
Figure 2.1 Example of a Decision Tree	7
Figure 2.2 Confusion Matrix for Binary Classification Problem.....	13
Figure 3.1 Conceptual Block Diagram	16
Figure 3.2 Description of Adult Data Set	18
Figure 3.3 Description of numerical attributes of Adult Data Set.....	19
Figure 3.4 Histogram depicting the nature of numerical attributes.....	19
Figure 3.5 Relation between workClass and income	20
Figure 3.6 Relation between occupation and income.....	20
Figure 3.7 Categorical values encoded into numerical values.....	21
Figure 3.8 Feature attributes after scaling	21
Figure 3.9 Description of the Breast Cancer Data Set.....	22
Figure 3.10 Description of numerical attributes of Breast Cancer Data Set.....	23
Figure 3.11 Description of class labels of Breast Cancer Data Set.	23
Figure 3.12 Correlation between attributes of Breast Cancer Data Set.....	24
Figure 3.13 Correlation between attributes after dropping some attributes	26
Figure 3.14 Description of the Car Evaluation data set.....	27
Figure 3.15 Frequency of categories in each columns	27
Figure 3.16 Frequency of categories in class label decision.....	28
Figure 3.17 Sample data of Car Evaluation data set	28
Figure 3.18 Sample data of Car Evaluation data set after Ordinal encoding.....	29
Figure 3.19 Description of the Heart Disease data set	29
Figure 3.20 Distribution of class label target.....	30
Figure 3.21 Distribution of attribute sex.....	31
Figure 3.22 Frequency of Heart Disease plotted against age.....	31
Figure 3.23 Frequency of Heart Disease for Sex	31
Figure 3.24 Correlation between different attributes with each other.	32
Figure 3.25 Correlation between different attributes with target.	33

Figure 3.26 Adding dummy variables to categorical variables.....	33
Figure 3.27 Scaling continuous variables.....	33
Figure 3.28 Description of the Iris Data Set.....	34
Figure 3.29 Description of the numerical attributes of Iris Data Set.....	34
Figure 3.30 Pair plot across all features.....	35
Figure 3.31 Correlation between different attributes with each other.....	36
Figure 3.32 Description of the Wine data set.....	36
Figure 3.33 Description of the numerical attributes of Wine data set.....	37
Figure 3.34 Correlation between attributes of Wine data set.....	37
Figure 4.1 Confusion Matrix of CART on Adult Data Set.....	38
Figure 4.2 Number of k in kNN vs. Accuracy.....	39
Figure 4.3 Confusion Matrix of kNN Classifier on Adult Data Set.....	40
Figure 4.4 Confusion Matrix of Naïve Bayesian Classifier on Adult Data Set.....	41
Figure 4.5 Confusion Matrix of SVM on Adult Data Set.....	42
Figure 4.6 Confusion Matrix of MLP Classifier on Adult Data Set.....	43
Figure 4.7 Confusion Matrix of CART on Breast Cancer Data Set.....	44
Figure 4.8 Number of k in kNN vs. Accuracy.....	45
Figure 4.9 Confusion Matrix of kNN Classifier on Breast Cancer Data Set.....	46
Figure 4.10 Confusion Matrix of Naïve Bayesian Classifier on Adult Data Set.....	47
Figure 4.11 Confusion Matrix of SVM on Breast Cancer Data Set.....	48
Figure 4.12 Confusion Matrix of MLP Classifier on Breast Cancer Data Set.....	49
Figure 4.13 Confusion Matrix of CART on Car Evaluation Data Set.....	50
Figure 4.14 Number of k in kNN vs. Accuracy.....	51
Figure 4.15 Confusion Matrix of kNN Classifier on Car Evaluation Data Set.....	52
Figure 4.16 Confusion Matrix of NB on Car Evaluation Data Set.....	53
Figure 4.17 Confusion Matrix of SVM on Car Evaluation Data Set.....	54
Figure 4.18 Confusion Matrix of MLP Classifier on Car Evaluation Data Set.....	55
Figure 4.19 Confusion Matrix of CART on Heart Disease Data Set.....	56
Figure 4.20 Number of k in kNN vs. Accuracy.....	57
Figure 4.21 Confusion Matrix of kNN Classifier on Heart Disease Data Set.....	58
Figure 4. 22 Confusion Matrix of NB on Heart Disease Data Set.....	59

Figure 4.23 Confusion Matrix of SVM on Heart Disease Data Set.....	60
Figure 4.24 Confusion Matrix of MLP Classifier on Heart Disease Data Set.....	61
Figure 4.25 Confusion Matrix of CART on Iris Data Set.....	62
Figure 4.26 Number of k in kNN vs. Accuracy	63
Figure 4.27 Confusion Matrix of kNN Classifier on Iris Data Set	64
Figure 4.28 Confusion Matrix of Naïve Bayesian Classifier on Iris Data Set.....	65
Figure 4.29 Confusion Matrix of SVM on Iris Data Set	66
Figure 4.30 Confusion Matrix of MLP Classifier on Iris Data Set.....	67
Figure 4.31 Confusion Matrix of CART on Wine Data Set.....	68
Figure 4.32 Number of k in kNN vs. Accuracy	69
Figure 4.33 Confusion Matrix of kNN Classifier on Wine Data Set	70
Figure 4.34 Confusion Matrix of Naïve Bayesian Classifier on Wine Data Set.....	71
Figure 4.35 Confusion Matrix of SVM on Wine Data Set	72
Figure 4.36 Confusion Matrix of MLP Classifier on Wine Data Set	73
Figure 4.37 Performance Analysis on Adult Data Set.....	76
Figure 4.38 Performance Analysis on Breast Cancer Data Set.....	77
Figure 4.39 Performance Analysis on Car Evaluation Data Set	78
Figure 4.40 Performance Analysis on Heart Disease Data Set.....	79
Figure 4.41 Performance Analysis on Iris Data Set	80
Figure 4.42 Performance Analysis on Wine Data Set	81
Figure 4.43 Training Time and Prediction Time across different data sets	82
Figure 4.44 Space Consumed by Various Classifiers in Various Data Set	83

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

IoT: Internet Of Things

CART: Classification and Regression Trees

kNN: k-Nearest Neighbours

SVM: Support Vector Machines

ANN: Artificial Neural Networks

MLP: Multi Layer Perceptron

MCC: Matthews Correlation Coefficient

1. INTRODUCTION

Data mining is a process of extracting or mining useful knowledge from a huge amount of data. It is a technique which is used primarily for finding out the previously unknown patterns and uncovers understandable information from a raw data. An enormous quantity of data is generated in this age of information across multiple areas. The usage of such data can play a vital role in knowledge discovery and decision support. Data mining is the process of identifying interesting patterns from large databases.

Data mining has already been applied in several aspects of our lives successfully. In case of business applications, many institutions use data mining to hold or gain a competitive edge. Data mining has been also used in database marketing in banks, retail data analysis on data collected from supermarkets, stock selection by investment companies, credit approval before providing loan, etc. Data mining has also been used in astronomy, molecular biology, medicine, geology, health care management, tax fraud detection, money laundering monitoring and even sports [1]. The rise of internet and ubiquitous usage of computers and devices has resulted in generation of huge volume of data. The generation of data is going to increase exponentially as with the usage of IoT devices and penetration of the internet to the poorer nations. This vast swath of data needs to be processed and analyzed to uncover the information that might be useful to the concerned stakeholders. That is where data mining comes into place.

Data mining techniques can be supervised, unsupervised and semi supervised. In supervised techniques, we have data for which the class label is already known and we create a model based on those labels. We can use the created model to classify the data for which the labels are not known. In case of unsupervised techniques, we do not know the labels of the data beforehand and we try to classify the given data into groups based on the similarity of their attribute values. In case of semi supervised techniques, we use it primarily when we have a small set of labeled data and large set of unlabeled data.

Data mining tasks are generally categorized into predictive tasks and descriptive tasks. In case of predictive tasks, the aim is to predict a value of a target attribute based on the value of other attributes and in case of descriptive tasks, the aim is to derive patterns that summarize the underlying relationships in data. The predictive tasks can further be divided into classification and regression. Classification is used for discrete target variables and regression is used for continuous target variables[2]. Classification techniques are used to classify each tuple in a dataset into one of predefined set of classes or target attributes. The objective of classification is to accurately predict the target class for each tuple in the data set. For example, a classification model built on the various details of bank customers could be used to identify loan applicants as low, medium, or high credit risks[3]. Data mining is an emerging field and there are many challenges yet to be conquered. Classification is one of the major aspects of data mining and due to the enormous volume of the data that is generated on a daily basis; it has become necessary to mine the data in an efficient and effective manner. The selection of a particular technique will be pivotal in the application area and. The selection of a particular technique for classification depends upon various parameters and the choice depends on the understanding of the data scientist and usually, a huge amount of time is wasted to apply every single classification technique with the hope of finding the best technique which fits the current need. Hence, there is a need for a data scientist to know which classification technique performs the best for a particular type of a data set. In this thesis, a comprehensive study of various classification techniques used in data mining is performed which will be of great help to both the beginners and experts working in this field by aiding them to choose the best classification approach to solve data mining problems.

1.1 STRUCTURE OF THE THESIS

The introduction of the thesis is covered in chapter 1. It explains the concept of data mining and its significance and elucidates the problem statement and research objective of this thesis work. It also highlights the current trends and the contributions of this thesis to the world. In chapter 2, a complete literature review on all the aspects of the subject covered by this thesis is presented. This comprises of the review of literature on the concept of data mining, the classification techniques of data mining

and the comparison of these techniques. In chapter 3, the design and implementation process of this research work is depicted. It includes the entire process starting from the loading of data sets, the preliminary analysis of the data set, the preprocessing performed on the data set before the models are created for analysis and comparison, and the process of creating the models. In chapter 4, the results of different model on various data sets are depicted and compared across several criteria. It also highlights and summarizes the results and gives the comparative analysis across each data set. Chapter 5 presents the conclusion of this thesis work and chapter 6 includes some possible areas for further research and future work.

1.2 BACKGROUND AND SIGNIFICANCE

Due to the rapid advancement in the use of internet, there is a huge amount of data that is being generated every day. This has resulted in a large amount of unprocessed information. It is quite tedious and time consuming to extract and view the relevant information from the vast trove of data that is generated. Thus, there is a need to develop a set of strategies which can aid us in obtaining the necessary information. To develop such set of strategies, the concept of data mining is used. The techniques of data mining help us to acquire the relevant patterns and information from the data. The data mining process is further elucidated by the block diagram in figure 1.1

Figure 1.1 The Data Mining Process

Data mining techniques can be used to uncover association between the entities, can be used to predict and classify. Data mining techniques can be supervised,

unsupervised and semi supervised. In supervised techniques, we have data for which the class label is already known and we create a model based on those labels. We can use the created model to classify the data for which the labels are not known. In case of unsupervised techniques, we do not know the labels of the data beforehand and we try to classify the given data into groups based on the similarity of their attribute values. In case of semi supervised techniques, we use it primarily when we have a small set of labeled data and large set of unlabeled data.

Classification is one of the major tasks in data mining. The idea behind classification is to label the given data records into one of the many possible cases which are known already. Classification can be seen as a supervised technique in which each tuple belongs to a class which is indicated as a class attribute. Classification requires predicting a certain outcome based on a given input. We categorize the data into training set and test set. We create a model based on the training set as depicted in Fig 1.2. After creating a model we can test the model on the test set. This way we can get an insight about how our model performs on a previously unseen data [4].

Figure 1.2 Model Construction and Test/Use

Different classifiers possess different quality which separates it from other classifiers. While performing analysis of classifiers we need to study their characteristics. The characteristics of a classifier are listed below:

- a) **Correctness:** This refers to how many of the tuple can a classifier classify correctly. We see the number of correctly classified tuples and incorrectly classified tuples and use several performance metrics to infer correctness.
- b) **Time Requirement:** Time requirement of a classifier refers to how much time is spent while constructing the model (training) and how much time does the model uses to classify the tuples.
- c) **Strength:** This refers to the ability of a classifier to classify a tuple correctly even when tuple has noise. Noise can be in several forms such as wrong value or missing value.
- d) **Data Size:** The classifiers used for classification should not depend upon size of the data sets. The model created should be scalable and the performance of the model should not be dependent on the size of the data set.
- e) **Extendibility:** If there is a need of adding a new feature then it should be possible. This characteristic is difficult to implement.

Data mining is an emerging field and there are many challenges yet to be conquered. Due to the enormous volume of the data that is generated on a daily basis, it has become necessary to find the right data mining technique for classification.

1.3 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Classification is one of the major aspects of data mining. In data mining, the selection of a particular technique to be used on a certain data set depends on the understanding of the data scientist and usually, a huge amount of time is wasted to apply every single classification technique with the hope of finding the best technique which fits the current need. Hence, there is a need for a data scientist to know which classification technique performs the best for a particular type of a data set.

In this thesis Decision Trees, K-Nearest Neighbor, Naive Bayes, Support Vector Machine and Artificial Neural Network classification techniques will be used on Iris, Heart Disease, Wine, Car Evaluation, Adult, Breast Cancer Wisconsin (Diagnostic) data sets to compare the classification outcomes of these techniques based on aforementioned characteristics.

Finally, the pros and cons of the techniques will be thoroughly discussed. This comprehensive study of various classification techniques used in data mining will be

of great help to both the beginners and experts working in this field by aiding them to choose the best classification approach to solve data mining problems.

1.4 OBJECTIVES

- a) To perform comprehensive analysis of different data mining techniques used in classification on multiple data sets of different nature.
- b) To identify classification techniques that performs the best for a given type of data set so that it can be employed directly without resorting to the usual trial-and-error approach.

1.5 CONTRIBUTIONS OF THE THESIS

There is a need to mine and analyze the huge amount of data that is generated every day. Data is ubiquitous and so is the need to mine the data. To analyze the vast swath of data, people employ many data mining technique among which classification is also one of the major techniques.

The data scientists and other related stakeholders are searching for the right set of tools and techniques to solving data-mining problems that require classification. This thesis work will give some valuable insight to those individuals who need to know about the choice of right classification techniques.

The result of this is the identification of the technique that performs in the best way for a given type of data set. This helps the concerned party to use the technique directly instead of relying on the usual trial-and-error approach. This process when effectively used will reduce the time required in building models for classification. Last but not the least this thesis work will be fruitful in identifying the very important performance measures and model evaluation criteria of classification techniques in data-mining.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter encompasses the literature review of this thesis work. It explains the existing research pertaining to the classification in data mining and the comparative analysis of different data mining algorithms.

2.1 OVERVIEW OF THE CLASSIFICATION TECHNIQUES TO BE COMPARED

There are several data mining techniques used for classification but in this thesis work, Decision Trees, KNN, Naïve Bayesian Classifier, SVM and ANN will be analyzed and compared.

- a) *Decision Trees*: Decision Tree is a tree which has a tree structure like a flowchart. It comprises of internal nodes and comprised of a decision which represents a test on an attribute, branches which represents an outcome of the test and leaf nodes which represents class labels. Suppose that, we want to classify a tuple X, the attribute values of X are tested against the decision tree. While testing a path is from the root note to a leaf node is traced and the leaf node at the end of the path signifies the class prediction for the tuple. Decision trees are often used because of their ability to be converted into classification rules and they can be constructed relatively fast compared to other classification techniques. The concept of decision trees is further elucidated by a decision tree example in figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1 Example of a Decision Tree

There are various algorithms to construct decision trees. They are ID3, C 4.5, and CART etc. We will use CART to construct decision trees in this thesis

because of its non probabilistic assumption and ability to support both numerical and categorical data[5].

- b) **K-Nearest Neighbors:** k-Nearest neighbor classifiers are one of the simplest classifiers. In this classification technique, the training samples are described by n dimensional numeric attributes. Each sample represents a point in an n-dimensional space. In this way, all of the training samples are stored in an n-dimensional pattern space. When the classifier is provided with an unknown sample, it searches the pattern space for the k training samples that are closest to the unknown sample[6]. "Closeness" is defined in terms of Euclidean distance, where the Euclidean distance between two points, $X=(x_1, x_2... x_n)$ and $Y=(y_1, y_2... y_n)$ is

$$d(X, Y) = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - y_i)^2}$$

In kNN, an object is classified by a majority vote of its neighbors, with the object being assigned to the class most common among its k nearest neighbors. The value of k is positive and usually small. The value of k = 1 implies that the class label assigned to the object will be the class label of its nearest neighbor. The value of k plays a significant role in kNN. Smaller value of k will make the classifier susceptible to over fitting and would result in misclassification of some easy to classify situations. Larger value of k can also lead to misclassification.

- c) **Support Vector Machines:** SVM is a very effective data mining technique that can be employed for regression, classification and general pattern recognition. It is considered as one of the good classifier because of its ability to high generalize even in the case of the dimension of the input space becoming very high. For a data set which is linearly separable, SVM is a linear classification function that corresponds to a separating hyper plane $f(x)$ that passes through the middle of the two classes, separating the two. Initially developed for binary classification, now it has been efficiently extended for problems that require multi-class classification. SVM can also be used for data set which is not linearly separable by extending to learn non- linear decision functions by

first projecting the input data onto a high-dimensional feature space using kernel functions and formulating a linear classification problem in that feature space.

- d) *Naive Bayesian Classifier*: Naive Bayesian classifiers are based on Bayes theorem. These predict class based on probabilities. This is one of the simplest classification techniques and it works even when there is high dimensionality of the inputs. They can work better than sophisticated classification methods and are often used in bench marking new classifiers. Suppose D is a data set which has associated class labels. Each tuple is represented by an n -dimensional attributes, (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) . Suppose the number of classes is m represented by C_1, C_2, \dots, C_m . Given a tuple, X , the classifier will predict that X belongs to the class C_i having the highest posterior probability, conditioned on X . Mathematically, X belongs to C_i if and only if

$$P(C_i | X) > P(C_j | X) \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq m, j \neq i.$$

Thus we maximize $P(C_i | X)$. $P(X)$ is constant for all classes, only $P(X | C_i) P(C_i)$ need be maximized. If the class prior probabilities are not known, then it is commonly assumed that the classes are equally likely that is $P(C_1) = P(C_2) = P(C_3) = P(C_m)$. This is called the Naive assumption.

- e) *Artificial Neural Networks*: Artificial Neural networks are simplified model designed by motivation from the nature of computing performed by human brain. It is a highly interconnected network of large number of processing elements called neuron analogical to biological neurons present in our brain. A neuron combines input from the data from the data set with a set of coefficients also known as weights that either amplify or dampen that input thereby assigning significance to inputs with regard to the task the algorithm is trying to learn. These input-weight products are summed and then the sum is passed through a neuron's activation function, to determine whether and to what extent that signal should progress further through the network to affect the ultimate outcome, suppose, an act of classification. If the signal can pass through, the neuron is said to be "activated."

2.2 REVIEW OF ANALYSIS OF CLASSIFICATION TECHNIQUE IN DATA MINING

Classification in data mining is concerned with the tasks in which the output of the instances is those values which are discrete and unordered. In a survey of different classification algorithm[7], different classification algorithms like decision trees, rules based classifiers, Bayesian networks, KNN classifiers were discussed and it was concluded that the decision trees and Bayesian network have different operational profile i.e. when one is very accurate the other is not so accurate and vice versa and decision trees and rule classifiers have a similar operational profile.

Gibert et al.[8] attempted to classify the data mining technique to simplify the selection of right data mining technique. A conceptual map of the most common data mining techniques by identifying the decisional criteria used by human experts in real decisions was provided and a tool was created which used the idea of case-based reasoning approach. However, since the tool was based on CBR, the strong limitation was the need of a number of varied past experiences before it provided appropriate support to the most users.

M. Kumari et al. analyzed the classification techniques such as RIPPER classifier, decision tree, ANNs and SVM on cardiovascular disease dataset and compared them through performance metrics such as sensitivity, specificity, accuracy, error rate, true positive rate and true negative rate[9]. Accuracy of rule based RIPPER, decision tree, ANN and SVM were found to be 81.08%, 79.05%, 80.06% and 84.12% respectively and SVM outperformed others in accuracy, sensitivity, specificity and error rates.

In another study A. H Wahbeh et al. analyzed the data mining tools WEKA, KNIME, Tanagra and Orange over nine different data sets and different classification algorithms and concluded that WEKA toolkit was the best in terms of the ability to run the selected classifier [10]. In this study the focus was on finding the perfect data mining tool.

Anjali G. Jivani et al. conducted the comparison between Bayesian classifier, KNN and decision tree on breast cancer data set using WEKA tool using accuracy, time taken, relative absolute error and root relative squared error as performance metrics[11]. The aforementioned techniques were used to create a model of breast cancer data set and it was found that Naïve Bayes, a version of Bayesian classifier performed the best in terms of time and accuracy i.e. it took the lowest amount of time and yet providing the highest accuracy. The comparison was done only on one data set and this cannot be generalized.

Another study used Rapid Miner and WEKA , which are open source software, to load 3 data sets and applied C 4.5, Naïve Bayes, KNN, ANN and SVM classification techniques[12] however the findings were not posted effectively in an articulate way and it provided no any solid conclusions. A similar work was done by L. C. Borges et al. [13] in which 8 different data sets were loaded in WEKA, KNIME, Orange and Rapid Miner and the accuracy of 6 different classification techniques were computed. The best result was achieved with WEKA using decision tree classification technique. The tools and the classification were compared on the basis of accuracy only.

Umadevi et al. [14] discussed the basic theoretical concepts of various classification techniques used in data mining and concluded that several performance metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall and f1-score can be used to evaluate the models. It was also concluded that decision tree algorithm should be used when the user doesn't know the in depth knowledge of the domain, SVM should be used in the context of minimum execution time and Naïve Bayes should be used if the application follows independent feature model. However, no experimental results were provided.

2.3 MODEL ANALYSIS CRITERIA

The paper published by Fayyad et al. discusses properties such as validity, understandability and usability[15]. Such characteristics can be used to analyze the several data mining techniques. For instance, we can say that a data mining technique is more superior to another one if it is more understandable or valid. If we can quantify such metrics then we can use them to evaluate data mining techniques. But some of the properties like usability cannot be measured and are subjective.

To fairly evaluate and compare the several data mining techniques in classification we need to consider several properties encompassing both positive and negative properties. We will use the following criteria for the analysis of the aforementioned classification techniques.

Classification Accuracy: This term is often called merely accuracy and is the most widely used metric. It is the ratio of number of correct prediction to the number of input samples in the dataset.

$$Accuracy = \frac{\text{Total No. of Correct Predictions}}{\text{Total No. of Predictions Made}}$$

Precision: Accuracy is one of the simplest and most widely used metric to measure the performance of a classifier. However accuracy is not always a good way to assess our model especially when our data is imbalanced. For instance we might have a dataset where the negative class is dominant over the positive class and we can obtain high accuracy so long as we predict negative most of the time. But such systems will have precision of 50% or less [16]. Precision represents the quality of positive prediction made by the model. It is the ratio of the number of correct positives predicted by the model to the total number of positive predictions. Precision is a good metric which can be used to select a model when the cost of false positive is high.

$$Precision = \frac{\text{No. of True Positives}}{\text{No. of True Positives} + \text{No. of False Positives}}$$

Recall: This metric represents the number of true positives found by the model. It is the ratio of the number of correct positives predicted by the model to the number of actual positives. Recall is a good metric which can be used to select a model when the cost of false negative is high.

$$Recall = \frac{No. of True Positives}{No. of True Positives + No. of False Negatives}$$

F1 Score: This metric is the harmonic mean of precision and recall. This metric can be quite useful when we want to seek a balance between the precision metric and recall metric.

$$F1\ Score = 2 * \frac{Precision * Recall}{Precision + Recall}$$

Confusion Matrix: This metric depicts number of instances where the model correctly classified a class as well as the number of instances where the model incorrectly classified a class. It is a matrix of order N x N where N is the number of target classes. It is extremely useful in giving us a holistic view of how well our classification model is doing and the errors made by it. For a binary classification problem, we have a matrix of order 2 x 2 as shown below:

		Actual Values	
		Positive	Negative
Predicted Values	Positive	True Positives	False Positives
	Negative	False Negatives	True Negatives

Figure 2.2 Confusion Matrix for Binary Classification Problem

Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC): This metric is used as a measure of the quality of binary and multiclass classification models. This metric considers both true and false positives and negatives and is generally regarded as a balanced measure which can be used even if the classes are of different sizes. It actually is a correlation

coefficient which values lies in the range of -1 and +1. MCC of +1 represents a perfect prediction by the model, MCC of 0 represents an average random prediction and MCC of -1 represents an inverse prediction. A study published in 2020 [17] showed that MCC produces a score which is more informative and truthful than accuracy and F1 score.

Big O Notation: This notation is used to describe the worst case time and space complexity of an algorithm as a function of size of the input. A function $f(n)$ is said to be the $O(g(n))$ (Big O of another function $g(n)$) if there exists c and n_0 such that $f(n) \leq c * g(n)$ for all $c > 0$ and $n \geq n_0$. It is one of the most fundamental tools used in the analysis of algorithms.

3. METHODOLOGY

In this chapter, the design and implementation of the thesis work is elucidated. The data sets were loaded and all the aforementioned data mining techniques were implemented on each data set. This chapter encompasses the entire process undertaken in thesis work.

3.1 PROCEDURE

The conceptual block diagram of this thesis work is depicted in Figure 3.1. The six data sets are first loaded and preliminary analysis is done on each data sets to gain invaluable insights about their properties. The relationship of the input attributes over the class labels is uncovered by plotting the input data over the output class label data. Then, the data preprocessing is performed on the data sets to reduce the level of dispersion between the data set's variables. The categorical attributes are encoded to numerical attributes to ensure that all classifiers can work. Scaling is performed on the data to make sure that the data between different attributes do not vary widely. The attributes which has no effect on the output class labels are also removed.

After data preprocessing is completed, each data sets are divided into two parts, training set and test set. The training set of each data set is used to build the model for each classification technique. So, six models were built for each data set. Then the model is validated by using the test set and to make sure that there is no bias, cross validation will be performed. The results of the model being tested on the test set are tabulated in the tables. The results of the model on training set are not depicted because it is of no relevance to this study.

Finally, all the aforementioned classification techniques are compared based on their results on each data set. The model evaluation criteria like accuracy, precision, recall and F1 score were used to evaluate the performance of model. The classification techniques were compared on other aspects such as speed, robustness, scalability and interpretability. The output of the thorough analysis is depicted in chapter 4 of this thesis.

Figure 3.1 Conceptual Block Diagram

3.2 DATA INTRODUCTION

Six different and unique data sets are used in this thesis work. These data sets were collected from the University of California Irvine's web portal[18]. University of California Irvine maintains 588 data sets as a service to the machine learning community and these can be downloaded and used for free. The data sets used were Adult data set[19], Breast Cancer Wisconsin (Diagnostic) data set[20], Car Evaluation data set[21], Heart Disease data set[22], Iris data set[23], Wine data set[24].

For the purpose of this work, we will be using Python programming language along with its libraries. Numpy[25] and Scipy[26] will be used for computation, Matplotlib[27], Seaborn[28] would be used for plotting data, pandas[29] will be used to load and manipulate the data, scikit learn[30] will be used for building models and computing various performance metric etc. Before any of the classification techniques were used on these data sets, they were loaded and initial analysis of the data attributes and class labels was performed. This is also one of the important aspects that needs to be done before the data is ready to be mined. It will give the idea about the nature of data and will be pivotal in aiding the data scientist to choose a particular classification technique.

3.3 PRELIMINARY ANALYSIS OF DATA AND PREPROCESSING

Each of the data sets were plotted to decipher the nature and relationship among various components of data. The inputs attributes were plotted against the output class label for each of the six data set to get acquainted with the relationship between the input attributes and class labels. The data sets were loaded and their description was plotted to see the number of numerical and categorical attributes. Categorical labels were encoded into numerical labels and after that the numerical labels were scaled. The attributes which were redundant or did not affect class labels were removed from the loaded data.

3.3.1 ADULT DATA SET

This data set was downloaded from the UCI Machine Learning Repository. This data set contains the information collected from the 1994 Census database. The data comprises of 14 attributes and contains 48,842 instances. The aim of classification in

this data set is to find out whether income exceeds \$50,000 per year. This data set has a good blend of categorical, numerical and missing values. The attributes and class label is depicted below in Figure 3.2.

```

<class 'pandas.core.frame.DataFrame'>
RangeIndex: 48843 entries, 0 to 48842
Data columns (total 15 columns):
#   Column                Non-Null Count  Dtype
---  -
0   age                   48843 non-null  object
1   workClass             46044 non-null  object
2   fnlwgt                48843 non-null  object
3   education             48843 non-null  object
4   education-num        48843 non-null  object
5   marital-status       48843 non-null  object
6   occupation            46034 non-null  object
7   relationship         48843 non-null  object
8   race                 48843 non-null  object
9   sex                  48843 non-null  object
10  capital-gain         48843 non-null  object
11  capital-loss         48843 non-null  object
12  hours-per-week       48843 non-null  object
13  native-country       47986 non-null  object
14  income               48843 non-null  object
dtypes: object(15)
memory usage: 5.6+ MB

```

Figure 3.2 Description of Adult Data Set

There are altogether 48,842 samples in the data set. The data set contains both categorical and numerical columns. And the columns like workClass, occupation and native-country have missing values. Now the numerical and categorical values are described separately. Numerical attributes were age, fnlwgt, education-num, capital-gain, capital-loss, hours-per-week. The age attributes represents age, fnlwgt represents sampling weight, education-num represents number of years spent in education, capital-gain and capital-loss represents income from capital sources and hours-per-week represents the number of hours-per-week worked. The attribute fnlwgt has no relation to the target label income and was removed before building the model. The numerical attributes are further elucidated by their description in Figure 3.3 and by histograms in Figure 3.4.

	age	fnlwgt	education-num	capital-gain	capital-loss	hours-per-week
count	32561.000000	3.256100e+04	32561.000000	32561.000000	32561.000000	32561.000000
mean	38.581647	1.897784e+05	10.080679	1077.648844	87.303830	40.437456
std	13.640433	1.055500e+05	2.572720	7385.292085	402.960219	12.347429
min	17.000000	1.228500e+04	1.000000	0.000000	0.000000	1.000000
25%	28.000000	1.178270e+05	9.000000	0.000000	0.000000	40.000000
50%	37.000000	1.783560e+05	10.000000	0.000000	0.000000	40.000000
75%	48.000000	2.370510e+05	12.000000	0.000000	0.000000	45.000000
max	90.000000	1.484705e+06	16.000000	99999.000000	4356.000000	99.000000

Figure 3.3 Description of numerical attributes of Adult Data Set.

From Figure 3.3 it was known that none of the numerical attributes had missing values but the values were on different scales. Since many data mining classification techniques require the values to be on same scale, the values were scaled using StandardScaler from the sklearn library.

Figure 3.4 Histogram depicting the nature of numerical attributes

In the data set, the categorical attributes are workClass, education, marital-status, occupation, relationship, race, sex, native-country and income. Income is also the class label that we are trying to predict. It was observed that the categorical column education was merely a string form of the numerical column education-num. Hence, it was dropped. The categorical attributes workClass, occupation and native-country had missing values so the missing values in these columns were replaced by the most frequent value occurring in that column. The categorical data are visualized in Figure 3.5 and 3.6.

Figure 3.5 Relation between workClass and income

Figure 3.6 Relation between occupation and income

The numerical attributes were scaled and the missing values in some of the categorical columns were filled. Then, the categorical values were encoded into numerical values which are depicted in Figure 3.7 and the scaled data set is depicted in Figure 3.8.

	age	workClass	education-num	marital-status	occupation	relationship	race	sex	capital-gain	capital-loss	hours-per-week	native-country
0	39	6	13	4	0	1	4	1	2174	0	40	38
1	50	5	13	2	3	0	4	1	0	0	13	38
2	38	3	9	0	5	1	4	1	0	0	40	38
3	53	3	7	2	5	0	2	1	0	0	40	38
4	28	3	13	2	9	5	2	0	0	0	40	4

Figure 3.7 Categorical values encoded into numerical values

	age	workClass	education-num	marital-status	occupation	relationship	race	sex	capital-gain	capital-loss	hours-per-week
0	0.030671	2.624298	1.134739	0.921634	-1.545256	-0.277805	0.393668	0.703071	0.148453	-0.21666	-0.035429
1	0.837109	1.721100	1.134739	-0.406212	-0.790092	-0.900181	0.393668	0.703071	-0.145920	-0.21666	-2.222153
2	-0.042642	-0.085296	-0.420060	-1.734058	-0.286649	-0.277805	0.393668	0.703071	-0.145920	-0.21666	-0.035429
3	1.057047	-0.085296	-1.197459	-0.406212	-0.286649	-0.900181	-1.962621	0.703071	-0.145920	-0.21666	-0.035429
4	-0.775768	-0.085296	1.134739	-0.406212	0.720237	2.211698	-1.962621	-1.422331	-0.145920	-0.21666	-0.035429

Figure 3.8 Feature attributes after scaling

Finally, the data set was fit to be trained and tested and was splitted into training set comprising of 66.67% of data and test set comprising of 33.33% of data. Several models were built using the aforementioned classification technique and analysis was done. The results are tabulated in chapter 4.

3.3.2 BREAST CANCER DATA SET

This data set was downloaded from the UCI Machine Learning Repository. This data set contains the information computed from a digitized image of a fine needle aspirate(FNA) of a breast mass which describes the characteristics of the cell nuclei present in the image. The data comprises of 32 attributes and contains 569 instances. The aim of classification in this data set is to find out whether the breast tissues are

malignant or benign. This data set has a good blend of categorical, numerical and missing values. The attributes and class label is depicted in Figure 3.9.

```
<class 'pandas.core.frame.DataFrame'>
RangeIndex: 569 entries, 0 to 568
Data columns (total 33 columns):
#   Column                                Non-Null Count  Dtype
---  -
0   id                                     569 non-null    int64
1   diagnosis                             569 non-null    object
2   radius_mean                           569 non-null    float64
3   texture_mean                           569 non-null    float64
4   perimeter_mean                         569 non-null    float64
5   area_mean                              569 non-null    float64
6   smoothness_mean                        569 non-null    float64
7   compactness_mean                       569 non-null    float64
8   concavity_mean                         569 non-null    float64
9   concave points_mean                    569 non-null    float64
10  symmetry_mean                           569 non-null    float64
11  fractal_dimension_mean                  569 non-null    float64
12  radius_se                               569 non-null    float64
13  texture_se                              569 non-null    float64
14  perimeter_se                            569 non-null    float64
15  area_se                                 569 non-null    float64
16  smoothness_se                           569 non-null    float64
17  compactness_se                           569 non-null    float64
18  concavity_se                             569 non-null    float64
19  concave points_se                       569 non-null    float64
20  symmetry_se                              569 non-null    float64
21  fractal_dimension_se                    569 non-null    float64
22  radius_worst                            569 non-null    float64
23  texture_worst                           569 non-null    float64
24  perimeter_worst                         569 non-null    float64
25  area_worst                              569 non-null    float64
26  smoothness_worst                        569 non-null    float64
27  compactness_worst                       569 non-null    float64
28  concavity_worst                         569 non-null    float64
29  concave points_worst                    569 non-null    float64
30  symmetry_worst                           569 non-null    float64
31  fractal_dimension_worst                 569 non-null    float64
32  Unnamed: 32                             0 non-null      float64
dtypes: float64(31), int64(1), object(1)
memory usage: 146.8+ KB
```

Figure 3.9 Description of the Breast Cancer Data Set

There are altogether 569 samples in the data set. The data set contains numerical columns and only the diagnosis column which is also the class label is categorical. Now the numerical values are described. From figure 3.9 it was clear that except Unnamed: 32 columns none of the numerical columns have missing values. It was deduced that the id has no use for the classification task. The Unnamed: 32 attribute feature included NaN so it had no need. Therefore id and Unnamed: 32 attribute features are dropped. The description of the remaining numerical columns is shown in figure 3.10

	radius_mean	texture_mean	perimeter_mean	area_mean	smoothness_mean	compactness_mean	concavity_mean	concave points_mean	s
count	569.000000	569.000000	569.000000	569.000000	569.000000	569.000000	569.000000	569.000000	
mean	14.127292	19.289649	91.969033	654.889104	0.096360	0.104341	0.088799	0.048919	
std	3.524049	4.301036	24.298981	351.914129	0.014064	0.052813	0.079720	0.038803	
min	6.981000	9.710000	43.790000	143.500000	0.052630	0.019380	0.000000	0.000000	
25%	11.700000	16.170000	75.170000	420.300000	0.086370	0.064920	0.029560	0.020310	
50%	13.370000	18.840000	86.240000	551.100000	0.095870	0.092630	0.061540	0.033500	
75%	15.780000	21.800000	104.100000	782.700000	0.105300	0.130400	0.130700	0.074000	
max	28.110000	39.280000	188.500000	2501.000000	0.163400	0.345400	0.426800	0.201200	

8 rows × 30 columns

Figure 3.10 Description of numerical attributes of Breast Cancer Data Set.

The number of Benign cases (B) and Malignant cases (M) are shown in Figure 3.11.

Figure 3.11 Description of class labels of Breast Cancer Data Set.

The attribute columns might be dependent on each other so to see if they are related, a correlation graph was drawn. Correlation of each attributes with other attributes was computed which is shown in Figure 3.12.

Figure 3.12 Correlation between attributes of Breast Cancer Data Set

It was seen in figure 3.12 that radius_mean, perimeter_mean and area_mean were correlated with each other so area_mean was used. In the same fashion, compactness_mean, concavity_mean and concave points_mean were correlated with each other. Therefore concavity_mean was chosen. Also, radius_se, perimeter_se and area_se were found to be correlated and area_se was used among them. In the similar manner radius_worst, perimeter_worst and area_worst were also found to be correlated so area_worst was used. Compactness_worst, concavity_worst and concave points_worst were also correlated so concavity_worst was used. Compactness_se, concavity_se and concave points_se were correlated so concavity_se was used. Likewise, texture_mean and texture_worst were correlated so use texture_mean was used. Also, area_worst and area_mean were correlated and area_mean was used.

So, the attributes columns that are to be used for classification are 'perimeter_mean', 'radius_mean', 'compactness_mean', 'concave points_mean', 'radius_se', 'perimeter_se', 'radius_worst', 'perimeter_worst', 'compactness_worst', 'concave points_worst', 'compactness_se', 'concave points_se', 'texture_worst', and 'area_worst' which are not correlated with each other as shown in figure 3.13.

Figure 3.13 Correlation between attributes after dropping some attributes

Now the data was divided into training set and test set with training set comprising of 66.67% of data and test set comprising of 33.33% of data. Since many data mining classification techniques require the values to be on same scale, the values were scaled using StandardScaler from the sklearn library and several models were built using the aforementioned classification technique and analysis was done. The results are tabulated in chapter 4.

3.3.3 CAR EVALUATION DATA SET

This data set was downloaded from the UCI Machine Learning Repository at <https://archive.ics.uci.edu/ml/datasets/Car+Evaluation>. The data set comprises of 6 attributes and contains 1728 instances. The aim of classification in this data set is to find out whether the decision is unacceptable, acceptable, good and very good based on the attributes. The attributes and class label is depicted in Figure 3.14.

```
<class 'pandas.core.frame.DataFrame'>
RangeIndex: 1728 entries, 0 to 1727
Data columns (total 7 columns):
#   Column          Non-Null Count  Dtype
---  ---            -
0   buying_price    1728 non-null   object
1   maint_cost      1728 non-null   object
2   nOfDoors        1728 non-null   object
3   nOfPersons      1728 non-null   object
4   lug_boot        1728 non-null   object
5   safety          1728 non-null   object
6   decision        1728 non-null   object
dtypes: object(7)
memory usage: 94.6+ KB
```

Figure 3.14 Description of the Car Evaluation data set

It can be seen that there are altogether 1728 samples in the data set. The data set contains categorical columns only and there are no missing values in the data set. The decision column is the class label. The frequency count of categories in attributes columns is depicted in figure 3.15.

```
vhigh    432
high     432
med      432
low      432
Name: buying_price, dtype: int64
vhigh    432
high     432
med      432
low      432
Name: maint_cost, dtype: int64
2        432
3        432
4        432
5more    432
Name: nOfDoors, dtype: int64
2        576
4        576
more     576
Name: nOfPersons, dtype: int64
small    576
med      576
big      576
Name: lug_boot, dtype: int64
low      576
med      576
high     576
Name: safety, dtype: int64
```

Figure 3.15 Frequency of categories in each columns

There are 6 attribute variables and a class label in the data set. All the variables are of categorical data type. The attribute variables are buying_price, maint_cost, nOfDoors, nOfPersons, lug_boot, safety and the class label is decision. The frequency count of categories in the class label decision is shown in Figure 3.16.

Figure 3.16 Frequency of categories in class label decision

The data set was differentiated into attributes columns and class label. Then the categorical columns were encoded into numerical values as depicted in Figure 3.17 and 3.18 using ordinal encoding which uses a single column of integers to represent the classes.

	buying_price	maint_cost	nOfDoors	nOfPersons	lug_boot	safety
1178	med	med	5more	4	big	high
585	high	high	3	more	small	low
1552	low	med	3	4	med	med
1169	med	med	5more	2	big	high
1033	med	high	4	2	big	med

Figure 3.17 Sample data of Car Evaluation data set

	buying_price	maint_cost	nOfDoors	nOfPersons	lug_boot	safety
1178	1	1	1	1	1	1
585	2	2	2	2	2	2
1552	3	1	2	1	3	3
1169	1	1	1	3	1	1
1033	1	2	3	3	1	3

Figure 3.18 Sample data of Car Evaluation data set after Ordinal encoding

Now the data was divided into training set and test set. Since many data mining classification techniques require the values to be on same scale, the values were scaled using StandardScaler from the sklearn library and several models were built using the aforementioned classification technique and analysis was done. The results are tabulated in chapter 4.

3.3.4 HEART DISEASE DATA SET

This data set was downloaded from the UCI Machine Learning Repository at <https://archive.ics.uci.edu/ml/datasets/Heart+Disease>. The data set comprises of 76 attributes out of which 14 attributes are normally used. The data set contains 303 instances. The aim of classification in this data set is to find out the presence of heart disease in the patient. The attributes and class label is depicted in Figure 3.19.

```
<class 'pandas.core.frame.DataFrame'>
RangeIndex: 303 entries, 0 to 302
Data columns (total 14 columns):
#   Column      Non-Null Count  Dtype
---  -
0   age         303 non-null    int64
1   sex         303 non-null    int64
2   cp          303 non-null    int64
3   trestbps    303 non-null    int64
4   chol        303 non-null    int64
5   fbs         303 non-null    int64
6   restecg     303 non-null    int64
7   thalach     303 non-null    int64
8   exang       303 non-null    int64
9   oldpeak     303 non-null    float64
10  slope       303 non-null    int64
11  ca          303 non-null    int64
12  thal        303 non-null    int64
13  target      303 non-null    int64
dtypes: float64(1), int64(13)
memory usage: 33.3 KB
```

Figure 3.19 Description of the Heart Disease data set

It can be seen that there are altogether 303 samples in the data set. There are no missing values in the data set. The target column is the class label. The data comprises of Data contains age which represents age of the patient in years, sex where 1 represents male and 0 represents female, cp which represents chest pain type , trestbps which represents resting blood pressure (in mm of Hg on admission of patient to the hospital), chol which represents serum cholesterol in mg per dl , fbs which represents fasting blood sugar > 120 mg per dl as 1 = true else 0 = false, restecg which represents resting electrocardiograph results , thalach which represents maximum heart rate achieved, exang which represents exercise induced angina where 1 = yes and 0 = no , oldpeak which represents ST depression induced by exercise relative to rest , slope which represents the slope of the peak exercise ST segment , ca which represents number of major vessels (0-3) colored by flourosopy , thal which represents 3 as normal; 6 as fixed defect; 7 as reversible defect and target which represents if there is a disease or not (1=yes, 0=no) . The distribution of class label target is shown in Figure 3.21.


```
Heart Disease: 165
No Heart Disease: 138
```

Figure 3.20 Distribution of class label target

The distributions of other attribute columns are also depicted in Fig 3.21, 3.22 and 3.23.

Male: 207
 Female: 96

Figure 3.21 Distribution of attribute sex

Figure 3.22 Frequency of Heart Disease plotted against age

Figure 3.23 Frequency of Heart Disease for Sex

Now the attributes are divided into categorical attribute and continuous attribute. The correlation matrix is constructed which depicts the correlation between attribute labels. Also, the correlation between attributes and class labels is depicted in Figure 3.24 and 3.25.

Figure 3.24 Correlation between different attributes with each other.

Figure 3.25 Correlation between different attributes with target.

From Figure 3.24 and 3.25 fbs and chol are the lowest correlated with the target variable and all other variables have a significant correlation with the target variable. There also was a need to convert some categorical variables into dummy variables as shown in Figure 3.26 and all the continuous values were scaled before creating the data mining classification models for the aforementioned classification techniques as shown in Figure 3.27.

	age	trestbps	chol	thalach	oldpeak	target	sex_0	sex_1	cp_0	cp_1	...	slope_2	ca_0	ca_1	ca_2	ca_3	ca_4	thal_0	thal_1	thal_2	thal_3
0	63	145	233	150	2.3	1	0	1	0	0	...	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
1	37	130	250	187	3.5	1	0	1	0	0	...	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
2	41	130	204	172	1.4	1	1	0	0	1	...	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
3	56	120	236	178	0.8	1	0	1	0	1	...	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
4	57	120	354	163	0.6	1	1	0	1	0	...	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0

Figure 3.26 Adding dummy variables to categorical variables

	age	trestbps	chol	thalach	oldpeak	target	sex_0	sex_1	cp_0	cp_1	...	slope_2	ca_0	ca_1	ca_2	ca_3	ca_4	thal_0	thal_1
0	0.952197	0.763956	-0.256334	0.015443	1.087338	1	0	1	0	0	...	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
1	-1.915313	-0.092738	0.072199	1.633471	2.122573	1	0	1	0	0	...	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	-1.474158	-0.092738	-0.816773	0.977514	0.310912	1	1	0	0	1	...	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	0.180175	-0.663867	-0.198357	1.239897	-0.206705	1	0	1	0	1	...	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
4	0.290464	-0.663867	2.082050	0.583939	-0.379244	1	1	0	1	0	...	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0

Figure 3.27 Scaling continuous variables

Now the data was divided into training set and test set. Several models were built using the aforementioned classification technique and analysis was done. The results are tabulated in chapter 4.

3.3.5 IRIS DATA SET

This data set was downloaded from the UCI Machine Learning Repository. The data set comprises of 5 columns and 150 instances. The class label has 3 categories of classes each having 50 instances , where each class represents a type of iris plant. One class is linearly separable from the other 2; the latter are NOT linearly separable from each other . The attributes and class label are depicted in Figure 3.28 and the description of the data set is depicted in Figure 3.29

```
<class 'pandas.core.frame.DataFrame'>
RangeIndex: 150 entries, 0 to 149
Data columns (total 5 columns):
#   Column          Non-Null Count  Dtype
---  -
0   SepalLengthCm   150 non-null    float64
1   SepalWidthCm    150 non-null    float64
2   PetalLengthCm   150 non-null    float64
3   PetalWidthCm    150 non-null    float64
4   Species         150 non-null    object
dtypes: float64(4), object(1)
memory usage: 6.0+ KB
```

Figure 3.28 Description of the Iris Data Set

	SepalLengthCm	SepalWidthCm	PetalLengthCm	PetalWidthCm
count	150.000000	150.000000	150.000000	150.000000
mean	5.843333	3.054000	3.758667	1.198667
std	0.828066	0.433594	1.764420	0.763161
min	4.300000	2.000000	1.000000	0.100000
25%	5.100000	2.800000	1.600000	0.300000
50%	5.800000	3.000000	4.350000	1.300000
75%	6.400000	3.300000	5.100000	1.800000
max	7.900000	4.400000	6.900000	2.500000

Figure 3.29 Description of the numerical attributes of Iris Data Set.

The columns in this dataset are SepalLengthCm, SepalWidthCm, PetalLengthCm, PetalWidthCm and Species is the class label. The distribution of data is further elucidated by pair plot in figure 3.31 which depicts that one of the class is linearly separable from the others and the remaining classes are not linearly separable. Iris-setosa is separated from the other two species across all of the combination of the features.

Figure 3.30 Pair plot across all features

Now, before creating a classification model, the number of features and the correlation between them is highly relevant. The presence of large numbers of highly correlated features will cause the training algorithm to reduce the accuracy. The correlation between the features of this data set is depicted in figure 3.31.

Figure 3.31 Correlation between different attributes with each other.

It is very clear from figure 3.31 that there is no correlation between SepalLengthCm and SepalWidthCm and PetalLengthCm and PetalWidthCm are highly correlated. The data set was splitted in training set and test set and Several models were built using the aforementioned classification technique and analysis was done. The results are tabulated in chapter 4.

3.3.6 WINE DATA SET

This data set was downloaded from the UCI Machine Learning Repository. The data set comprises of 13 attributes and 178 instances. The data set has 3 classes which represents three different types of wine. There are 59 instances of class 1 wine, 71 instance of class 2 wine and 48 instances of class 3 wine. The attributes and class label are depicted in Figure 3.32 and the description of the data set is depicted in Figure 3.33.

```
<class 'pandas.core.frame.DataFrame'>
RangeIndex: 178 entries, 0 to 177
Data columns (total 14 columns):
#   Column                Non-Null Count  Dtype
---  -
0   class                 178 non-null   int64
1   alcohol              178 non-null   float64
2   malic_acid           178 non-null   float64
3   ash                  178 non-null   float64
4   AlcalinityOfAsh     178 non-null   float64
5   magnesium            178 non-null   int64
6   total_phenols       178 non-null   float64
7   Flavanoids          178 non-null   float64
8   nonflavanoid phenols 178 non-null   float64
9   proanthocyanins     178 non-null   float64
10  color_intensity      178 non-null   float64
11  hue                  178 non-null   float64
12  OD280/OD315         178 non-null   float64
13  proline              178 non-null   int64
dtypes: float64(11), int64(3)
memory usage: 19.6 KB
```

Figure 3.32 Description of the wine data set

	alcohol	malic_acid	ash	AlcalinityOfAsh	magnesium	total_phenols	Flavanoids	nonflavanoid phenols	proanthocyanins	color_intensity
count	178.000000	178.000000	178.000000	178.000000	178.000000	178.000000	178.000000	178.000000	178.000000	178.000000
mean	13.000618	2.336348	2.366517	19.494944	99.741573	2.295112	2.029270	0.361854	1.590899	5.058090
std	0.811827	1.117146	0.274344	3.339564	14.282484	0.625851	0.998859	0.124453	0.572359	2.318286
min	11.030000	0.740000	1.360000	10.600000	70.000000	0.980000	0.340000	0.130000	0.410000	1.280000
25%	12.362500	1.602500	2.210000	17.200000	88.000000	1.742500	1.205000	0.270000	1.250000	3.220000
50%	13.050000	1.865000	2.360000	19.500000	98.000000	2.355000	2.135000	0.340000	1.555000	4.690000
75%	13.677500	3.082500	2.557500	21.500000	107.000000	2.800000	2.875000	0.437500	1.950000	6.200000
max	14.830000	5.800000	3.230000	30.000000	162.000000	3.880000	5.080000	0.660000	3.580000	13.000000

Figure 3.33 Description of the numerical attributes of Wine data set.

There are no missing values in the data set and all of the columns are numerical. The correlation between the features of this data set is depicted in figure 3.34.

Figure 3.34 Correlation between attributes of Wine data set.

It is seen that the attribute ash has no correlation with the class label. So, it is dropped. Then, the data is divided into training set and test set and several models were built.

4. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

In section three, different data sets used in this thesis work were introduced, described and the nature of the data sets were uncovered to gain a superficial insight on the attributes and target classes. In this section, a machine learning model will be built for each of the classification algorithms for each data set. Then, the output of the models will be compared and contrasted.

4.1 ANALYSIS ON ADULT DATA SET

The data set comprises of 14 attributes and contains 48,842 instances. The aim of classification in this data set is to find out whether income exceeds \$50,000 per year. In this section, the five aforementioned classification techniques will be applied to build a model on the adult data set.

4.1.1 Decision Trees (CART) Model on Adult Data Set

A machine learning model was constructed using CART (Classification and Regression Trees) algorithm. The accuracy was found to be 0.818. Furthermore, the confusion matrix is also depicted below showing the number of true positives (TP), true negatives (TN), false positives (FP) and false negatives (FN).

Figure 4.1 Confusion Matrix of CART on Adult Data Set

The precision, recall and f1 score for the class labels “<=50K” and “>50K” are depicted below

Metric	“<=50K”	“>50K”
Precision	0.876	0.620
Recall	0.887	0.594
F1 Score	0.881	0.606

Table 4.1 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of CART on Adult Data Set

Although, the accuracy was 0.818, CART had higher precision and recall on the class “<=50k” than on the “>50k”. This is because of the class imbalance.

The value of Matthews’s correlation coefficient (MCC) was found to be 0.488. It depicts a strong positive relationship between the actual class labels and predicted class labels.

4.1.2 KNN Classifier Model on Adult Data Set

A machine learning model was created where the values of different k were observed and the value which yielded the maximum accuracy score was used for further analysis.

Figure 4.2 Number of k in kNN vs. Accuracy

The accuracy of the model was found to be 0.842 for $k = 9$. Furthermore, the confusion matrix is also depicted below showing the number of true positives (TP), true negatives (TN), false positives (FP) and false negatives (FN).

Figure 4.3 Confusion Matrix of kNN Classifier on Adult Data Set

The precision, recall and f1 score for the class labels “ $\leq 50K$ ” and “ $> 50K$ ” are depicted below

Metric	“ $\leq 50K$ ”	“ $> 50K$ ”
Precision	0.880	0.690
Recall	0.917	0.597
F1 Score	0.898	0.641

Table 4.2 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of kNN on Adult Data Set

KNN also had higher precision and recall on the class “ $\leq 50k$ ” than on the “ $> 50k$ ”. The value of Matthews’s correlation coefficient (MCC) was found to be 0.542. It depicts a strong positive relationship between the actual class labels and predicted class labels.

4.1.3 Naïve Bayesian Classifier Model on Adult Data Set

A machine learning model was created using Naïve Bayes implementation which uses Gaussian probability distribution. The accuracy of the model was found to be 0.804. Furthermore, the confusion matrix is also depicted below showing the number of true positives (TP), true negatives (TN), false positives (FP) and false negatives (FN).

Figure 4.4 Confusion Matrix of Naïve Bayesian Classifier on Adult Data Set

The precision, recall and f1 score for the class labels “<=50K” and “>50K” are depicted below

Metric	“<=50K”	“>50K”
Precision	0.820	0.674
Recall	0.950	0.329
F1 Score	0.881	0.442

Table 4.3 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of Naïve Bayesian on Adult Data Set

Naïve Bayesian Classifier too had less precision and recall for “>50K” class.

The value of Matthews’s correlation coefficient (MCC) was found to be 0.373. It depicts a moderate positive relationship between the actual class labels and predicted class labels.

4.1.4 SVM Model on Adult Data Set

A machine learning model was created for SVM. The accuracy of the model was found to be 0.850. Furthermore, the confusion matrix is also depicted below showing the number of true positives (TP), true negatives (TN), false positives (FP) and false negatives (FN).

Figure 4.5 Confusion Matrix of SVM on Adult Data Set

The precision, recall and f1 score for the class labels “<=50K” and “>50K” are depicted below

Metric	“<=50K”	“>50K”
Precision	0.868	0.762
Recall	0.948	0.533
F1 Score	0.906	0.627

Table 4.4 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of SVM on Adult Data Set

The value of Matthews’s correlation coefficient (MCC) was found to be 0.550. It depicts a strong positive relationship between the actual class labels and predicted class labels.

4.1.5 ANN (MLP Classifier) Model on Adult Data Set

A machine learning model was created using Multi Layer Perceptron. The accuracy of the model was found to be 0.827. Furthermore, the confusion matrix is also depicted below showing the number of true positives (TP), true negatives (TN), false positives (FP) and false negatives (FN).

Figure 4.6 Confusion Matrix of MLP Classifier on Adult Data Set

The precision, recall and f1 score for the class labels “<=50K” and “>50K” are depicted below

Metric	“<=50K”	“>50K”
Precision	0.871	0.657
Recall	0.910	0.564
F1 Score	0.890	0.607

Table 4.5 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of MLP Classifier on Adult Data Set

The value of Matthews’s correlation coefficient (MCC) was found to be 0.500. It depicts a strong positive relationship between the actual class labels and predicted class labels.

4.2 ANALYSIS ON BREAST CANCER DATASET

The data comprises of 32 attributes and contains 569 instances. The aim of classification in this data set is to find out whether the breast tissues are malignant or benign. In this section, models will be built for the aforementioned classification techniques and analyzed.

4.2.1 Decision Trees (CART) Model on Breast Cancer Data Set

A machine learning model was constructed using CART (Classification and Regression Trees) algorithm. The accuracy was found to be 0.912. Furthermore, the confusion matrix is also depicted below

Figure 4.7 Confusion Matrix of CART on Breast Cancer Data Set

The precision, recall and f1 score for the class labels “Benign” and “Malignant” are depicted below

Metric	“Benign”	“Malignant”
Precision	0.951	0.853
Recall	0.907	0.920
F1 Score	0.929	0.885

Table 4.6 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of CART on Breast Cancer Data Set

The classes weren't as imbalanced as the Adult data set so the value of precision and recall were high for both the classes.

The value of Matthews's correlation coefficient (MCC) was found to be 0.816. It depicts a very strong positive relationship between the actual class labels and predicted class labels.

4.2.2 KNN Classifier Model on Breast Cancer Data Set

A machine learning model was created where the values of different k were observed and the value which yielded the maximum accuracy score was used for further analysis.

Figure 4.8 Number of k in kNN vs. Accuracy

The accuracy of the model was found to be 0.941 for $k = 4$. Furthermore, the confusion matrix is also depicted below.

Figure 4.9 Confusion Matrix of kNN Classifier on Breast Cancer Data Set

The precision, recall and f1 score for the class labels “Benign” and “Malignant” are depicted below

Metric	“Benign”	“Malignant”
Precision	0.9375	0.950
Recall	0.972	0.889
F1 Score	0.955	0.918

Table 4.7 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of kNN on Breast Cancer Data Set

The value of Matthews’s correlation coefficient (MCC) was found to be 0.873. It depicts a very strong positive relationship between the actual class labels and predicted class labels.

4.2.3 Naïve Bayesian Classifier Model on Breast Cancer Data Set

A machine learning model was created using Naïve Bayes implementation which uses Gaussian probability distribution. The accuracy of the model was found to be 0.930. Furthermore, the confusion matrix is also depicted below.

Figure 4.10 Confusion Matrix of Naïve Bayesian Classifier on Adult Data Set

The precision, recall and f1 score for the class labels “Benign” and “Malignant” are depicted below

Metric	“Benign”	“Malignant”
Precision	0.944	0.904
Recall	0.944	0.904
F1 Score	0.944	0.904

Table 4.8 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of NB on Breast Cancer Data Set

The value of Matthews’s correlation coefficient (MCC) was found to be 0.850. It depicts a very strong positive relationship between the actual class labels and predicted class labels.

4.2.4 SVM Model on Breast Cancer Data Set

A machine learning model was created for SVM. The accuracy of the model was found to be 0.947. Furthermore, the confusion matrix is also depicted below.

Figure 4.11 Confusion Matrix of SVM on Breast Cancer Data Set

The precision, recall and f1 score for the class labels “Benign” and “Malignant” are depicted below

Metric	“Benign”	“Malignant”
Precision	0.954	0.935
Recall	0.963	0.921
F1 Score	0.959	0.923

Table 4.9 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of SVM on Breast Cancer Data Set

The value of Matthews’s correlation coefficient (MCC) was found to be 0.887. It depicts a very strong positive relationship between the actual class labels and predicted class labels.

4.2.5 ANN (MLP Classifier) Model on Breast Cancer Data Set

A machine learning model was created using Multi Layer Perceptron. The accuracy of the model was found to be 0.960. Furthermore, the confusion matrix is also depicted below.

Figure 4.12 Confusion Matrix of MLP Classifier on Breast Cancer Data Set

The precision, recall and f1 score for the class labels “Benign” and “Malignant” are depicted below

Metric	“Benign”	“Malignant”
Precision	0.956	0.967
Recall	0.981	0.921
F1 Score	0.968	0.943

Table 4.10 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of MLP on Breast Cancer Data Set

The value of Matthews’s correlation coefficient (MCC) was found to be 0.912. It depicts a very strong positive relationship between the actual class labels and predicted class labels.

4.3 ANALYSIS ON CAR EVALUATION DATA SET

The data set comprises of 6 attributes and contains 1728 instances. The aim of classification in this data set is to find out whether the decision is unacceptable, acceptable, good and very good based on the attributes. We will be performing multi class classification in this data set.

4.3.1 Decision Trees (CART) Model on Car Evaluation Data Set

A machine learning model was constructed using CART (Classification and Regression Trees) algorithm. The accuracy was found to be 0.925. Furthermore, the confusion matrix is also depicted below

Figure 4.13 Confusion Matrix of CART on Car Evaluation Data Set

The precision, recall and f1 score for the class labels “Unacceptable” and “Acceptable”, “Good” and “Very Good” are depicted below

Metric	“Unacceptable”	“Acceptable”	“Good”	“Very Good”
Precision	0.905	0.640	0.967	0.667
Recall	0.813	0.842	0.983	0.667
F1 Score	0.857	0.727	0.975	0.667

Table 4.11 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of CART on Breast Cancer Data Set

There were more instances of data for the class labels “Unacceptable” and “Good” so the value of precision and recall was more for these class labels.

The value of Matthews’s correlation coefficient (MCC) was found to be 0.840. It depicts a very strong positive relationship between the actual class labels and predicted class labels.

4.3.2 KNN Classifier Model on Car Evaluation Data Set

A machine learning model was created where the values of different k were observed and the value which yielded the maximum accuracy score was used for further analysis.

Figure 4.14 Number of k in kNN vs. Accuracy

The accuracy of the model was found to be 0.846 for k = 5. Furthermore, the confusion matrix is also depicted below.

Figure 4.15 Confusion Matrix of kNN Classifier on Car Evaluation Data Set

The precision, recall and f1 score for the class labels “Unacceptable” and “Acceptable”, “Good” and “Very Good” are depicted below

Metric	“Unacceptable”	“Acceptable”	“Good”	“Very Good”
Precision	0.651	0.333	0.918	0.833
Recall	0.729	0.053	0.970	0.208
F1 Score	0.688	0.090	0.943	0.333

Table 4.12 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of kNN on Car Evaluation Data Set

The value of Matthews’s correlation coefficient (MCC) was found to be 0.654. It depicts a strong positive relationship between the actual class labels and predicted class labels.

4.3.3 Naïve Bayesian Classifier Model on Car Evaluation Data Set

A machine learning model was created using Naïve Bayes implementation which uses Gaussian probability distribution. The accuracy of the model was found to be 0.593. This classifier worked poorly on this data set. Furthermore, the confusion matrix is also depicted below.

Figure 4.16 Confusion Matrix of NB on Car Evaluation Data Set

The precision, recall and f1 score for the class labels “Unacceptable” and “Acceptable”, “Good” and “Very Good” are depicted below

Metric	“Unacceptable”	“Acceptable”	“Good”	“Very Good”
Precision	0.538	0.000	0.815	0.144
Recall	0.059	0.000	0.774	1.000
F1 Score	0.107	0.000	0.797	0.252

Table 4.13 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of NB on Car Evaluation Data Set

The value of Matthews’s correlation coefficient (MCC) was found to be 0.2584. It depicts a weak positive relationship between the actual class labels and predicted class labels.

4.3.4 SVM Model on Car Evaluation Data Set

A machine learning model was created for SVM. The accuracy of the model was found to be 0.805. Furthermore, the confusion matrix is also depicted below.

Figure 4.17 Confusion Matrix of SVM on Car Evaluation Data Set

The precision, recall and f1 score for the class labels “Unacceptable” and “Acceptable”, “Good” and “Very Good” are depicted below

Metric	“Unacceptable”	“Acceptable”	“Good”	“Very Good”
Precision	0.580	0.000	0.875	0.000
Recall	0.610	0.000	0.966	0.000
F1 Score	0.595	0.000	0.919	0.000

Table 4.14 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of SVM on Car Evaluation Data Set

The value of Matthews’s correlation coefficient (MCC) was found to be 0.547. It depicts a strong positive relationship between the actual class labels and predicted class labels.

4.3.5 ANN (MLP Classifier) Model on Car Evaluation Data Set

A machine learning model was created using Multi Layer Perceptron. The accuracy of the model was found to be 0.950. Furthermore, the confusion matrix is also depicted below.

Figure 4.18 Confusion Matrix of MLP Classifier on Car Evaluation Data Set

The precision, recall and f1 score for the class labels “Unacceptable” and “Acceptable”, “Good” and “Very Good” are depicted below.

Metric	“Unacceptable”	“Acceptable”	“Good”	“Very Good”
Precision	0.928	0.710	0.980	0.850
Recall	0.880	0.890	0.991	0.708
F1 Score	0.904	0.790	0.984	0.772

Table 4.15 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of MLP on Car Evaluation Data Set

The value of Matthews’s correlation coefficient (MCC) was found to be 0.892. It depicts a very strong positive relationship between the actual class labels and predicted class labels.

4.4 ANALYSIS ON HEART DISEASE DATA SET

This data set comprises of 14 attributes and 303 instances. The aim of classification in this data set is to find out the presence of heart disease in the patient. The class labels are 0 and 1. 0 represents the absence of heart disease and 1 represents the presence of heart disease. Since there are two classes, this is an example of binary classification. In this section, all aforementioned algorithms will be used to build models and will be analyzed.

4.4.1 Decision Trees (CART) Model on Heart Disease Data Set

A machine learning model was constructed using CART (Classification and Regression Trees) algorithm. The accuracy was found to be 1.00. Furthermore, the confusion matrix is also depicted below

Figure 4.19 Confusion Matrix of CART on Heart Disease Data Set

The precision, recall and f1 score for the class labels “0” and “1” are depicted below.

Metric	“0”	“1”
Precision	1.000	1.000
Recall	1.000	1.000
F1 Score	1.000	1.000

Table 4.16 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of CART on Heart Disease Data Set

The value of Matthews's correlation coefficient (MCC) was found to be 1.000 It depicts a very strong positive relationship between the actual class labels and predicted class labels.

4.4.2 KNN Classifier Model on Heart Disease Data Set

A machine learning model was created where the values of different k were observed and the value which yielded the maximum accuracy score was used for further analysis.

Figure 4.20 Number of k in kNN vs. Accuracy

The accuracy of the model was found to be 0.923 for $k = 18$. Furthermore, the confusion matrix is also depicted below.

Figure 4.21 Confusion Matrix of kNN Classifier on Heart Disease Data Set

The precision, recall and f1 score for the class labels “0” and “1” are depicted below.

Metric	“0”	“1”
Precision	0.925	0.922
Recall	0.902	0.940
F1 Score	0.913	0.930

Table 4.17 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of kNN on Heart Disease Data Set

The value of Matthews’s correlation coefficient (MCC) was found to be 0.844. It depicts a strong positive relationship between the actual class labels and predicted class labels.

4.4.3 Naïve Bayesian Classifier Model on Heart Disease Data Set

A machine learning model was created using Naïve Bayes implementation which uses Gaussian probability distribution. The accuracy of the model was found to be 1.000. Furthermore, the confusion matrix is also depicted below.

Figure 4. 22 Confusion Matrix of NB on Heart Disease Data Set

The precision, recall and f1 score for the class labels “0” and “1” are depicted below.

Metric	“0”	“1”
Precision	1.000	1.000
Recall	1.000	1.000
F1 Score	1.000	1.000

Table 4.18 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of NB on Heart Disease Data Set

The value of Matthews’s correlation coefficient (MCC) was found to be 1.000. It depicts a very strong positive relationship between the actual class labels and predicted class labels.

4.4.4 SVM Model on Heart Disease Data Set

A machine learning model was created for SVM. The accuracy of the model was found to be 0.967. Furthermore, the confusion matrix is also depicted below.

Figure 4.23 Confusion Matrix of SVM on Heart Disease Data Set

The precision, recall and f1 score for the class labels “0” and “1” are depicted below.

Metric	“0”	“1”
Precision	0.975	0.960
Recall	0.951	0.980
F1 Score	0.996	0.970

Table 4.19 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of SVM on Heart Disease Data Set

The value of Matthews’s correlation coefficient (MCC) was found to be 0.978. It depicts a strong positive relationship between the actual class labels and predicted class labels.

4.4.5 ANN (MLP Classifier) Model on Heart Disease Data Set

A machine learning model was created using Multi Layer Perceptron. The accuracy of the model was found to be 0.978. Furthermore, the confusion matrix is also depicted below.

Figure 4.24 Confusion Matrix of MLP Classifier on Heart Disease Data Set

The precision, recall and f1 score for the class labels “0” and “1” are depicted below.

Metric	“0”	“1”
Precision	0.975	0.980
Recall	0.975	0.980
F1 Score	0.975	0.980

Table 4.20 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of MLP on Heart Disease Data Set

The value of Matthews’s correlation coefficient (MCC) was found to be 0.955. It depicts a very strong positive relationship between the actual class labels and predicted class labels.

4.5 ANALYSIS ON IRIS DATA SET

This data set comprises of 150 entries and four attributes. The attributes are SepalLengthCm, SepalWidthCm, PetalLengthCm and PetalWidthCm. The aim of classification in this data set is to find out the species of the Iris flower. There are three target classes so this is an example of multi class classification. In this section, the aforementioned data mining techniques will be implemented on the Iris data set and they will be analyzed.

4.5.1 Decision Trees (CART) Model on Iris Data Set

A machine learning model was constructed using CART (Classification and Regression Trees) algorithm. The accuracy was found to be 1.000. Furthermore, the confusion matrix is also depicted below

Figure 4.25 Confusion Matrix of CART on Iris Data Set

The precision, recall and f1 score for the class labels “Iris-setosa”, “Iris-versicolor” and “Iris-virginica” are depicted below.

Metric	“Iris-setosa”	“Iris-versicolor”	“Iris-virginica”
Precision	1.000	1.000	1.000
Recall	1.000	1.000	1.000
F1 Score	1.000	1.000	1.000

Table 4.21 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of CART on Iris Data Set

The value of Matthews's correlation coefficient (MCC) was found to be 1.000. It depicts a very strong positive relationship between the actual class labels and predicted class labels.

4.5.2 KNN Classifier Model on Iris Data Set

A machine learning model was created where the values of different k were observed and the value which yielded the maximum accuracy score was used for further analysis.

Figure 4.26 Number of k in kNN vs. Accuracy

The accuracy of the model was found to be 1.000 for $k = 1$. Furthermore, the confusion matrix is also depicted below.

Figure 4.27 Confusion Matrix of kNN Classifier on Iris Data Set

The precision, recall and f1 score for the class labels “Iris-setosa”, “Iris-versicolor” and “Iris-virginica” are depicted below.

Metric	“Iris-setosa”	“Iris-versicolor”	“Iris-virginica”
Precision	1.000	1.000	1.000
Recall	1.000	1.000	1.000
F1 Score	1.000	1.000	1.000

Table 4.22 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of kNN on Iris Data Set

The value of Matthews’s correlation coefficient (MCC) was found to be 1.000. It depicts a strong positive relationship between the actual class labels and predicted class labels.

4.5.3 Naïve Bayesian Classifier Model on Iris Data Set

A machine learning model was created using Naïve Bayes implementation which uses Gaussian probability distribution. The accuracy of the model was found to be 0.977. Furthermore, the confusion matrix is also depicted below.

Figure 4.28 Confusion Matrix of Naïve Bayesian Classifier on Iris Data Set

The precision, recall and f1 score for the class labels “Iris-setosa”, “Iris-versicolor” and “Iris-virginica” are depicted below.

Metric	“Iris-setosa”	“Iris-versicolor”	“Iris-virginica”
Precision	1.000	1.000	0.928
Recall	1.000	0.923	1.000
F1 Score	1.000	0.960	0.963

Table 4.23 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of NB on Iris Data Set

The value of Matthews’s correlation coefficient (MCC) was found to be 0.967. It depicts a strong positive relationship between the actual class labels and predicted class labels.

4.5.4 SVM Model on Iris Data Set

A machine learning model was created for SVM. The accuracy of the model was found to be 1.000. Furthermore, the confusion matrix is also depicted below.

Figure 4.29 Confusion Matrix of SVM on Iris Data Set

The precision, recall and f1 score for the class labels “Iris-setosa”, “Iris-versicolor” and “Iris-virginica” are depicted below.

Metric	“Iris-setosa”	“Iris-versicolor”	“Iris-virginica”
Precision	1.000	1.000	1.000
Recall	1.000	1.000	1.000
F1 Score	1.000	1.000	1.000

Table 4.24 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of SVM on Iris Data Set

The value of Matthews’s correlation coefficient (MCC) was found to be 1.000. It depicts a strong positive relationship between the actual class labels and predicted class labels.

4.5.5 ANN (MLP Classifier) Model on Iris Data Set

A machine learning model was created using Multi Layer Perceptron. The accuracy of the model was found to be 1.000. Furthermore, the confusion matrix is also depicted below.

Figure 4.30 Confusion Matrix of MLP Classifier on Iris Data Set

The precision, recall and f1 score for the class labels “Iris-setosa”, “Iris-versicolor” and “Iris-virginica” are depicted below.

Metric	“Iris-setosa”	“Iris-versicolor”	“Iris-virginica”
Precision	1.000	1.000	1.000
Recall	1.000	1.000	1.000
F1 Score	1.000	1.000	1.000

Table 4.25 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of MLP on Iris Data Set

The value of Matthews’s correlation coefficient (MCC) was found to be 1.000. It depicts a very strong positive relationship between the actual class labels and predicted class labels.

4.6 ANALYSIS ON WINE DATA SET

This data set comprises of 178 entries and 13 attributes. The aim of classification in this data set is to find out the class of wine from these 13 attributes. There are 3 classes in this data set. In this section, all the aforementioned data mining classification will be used to build models and will be analyzed.

4.6.1 Decision Trees (CART) Model on Wine Data Set

A machine learning model was constructed using CART (Classification and Regression Trees) algorithm. The accuracy was found to be 0.962. Furthermore, the confusion matrix is also depicted below

Figure 4.31 Confusion Matrix of CART on Wine Data Set

The precision, recall and f1 score for the class labels “1”, “2” and “3” are depicted below.

Metric	“1”	“2”	“3”
Precision	0.947	0.945	1.000
Recall	0.947	1.000	0.928
F1 Score	0.947	0.976	0.962

Table 4.26 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of CART on Wine Data Set

The value of Matthews's correlation coefficient (MCC) was found to be 0.947. It depicts a very strong positive relationship between the actual class labels and predicted class labels.

4.6.2 KNN Classifier Model on Wine Data Set

A machine learning model was created where the values of different k were observed and the value which yielded the maximum accuracy score was used for further analysis.

Figure 4.32 Number of k in kNN vs. Accuracy

The accuracy of the model was found to be 0.796 for $k = 1$. Furthermore, the confusion matrix is also depicted below.

Figure 4.33 Confusion Matrix of kNN Classifier on Wine Data Set

The precision, recall and f1 score for the class labels “1”, “2” and “3” are depicted below.

Metric	“1”	“2”	“3”
Precision	0.809	0.842	0.714
Recall	0.894	0.761	0.714
F1 Score	0.850	0.800	0.714

Table 4.27 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of kNN on Wine Data Set

The value of Matthews’s correlation coefficient (MCC) was found to be 0.692. It depicts a strong positive relationship between the actual class labels and predicted class labels.

4.6.3 Naïve Bayesian Classifier Model on Wine Data Set

A machine learning model was created using Naïve Bayes implementation which uses Gaussian probability distribution. The accuracy of the model was found to be 1.000. Furthermore, the confusion matrix is also depicted below.

Figure 4.34 Confusion Matrix of Naïve Bayesian Classifier on Wine Data Set

The precision, recall and f1 score for the class labels “1”, “2” and “3” are depicted below.

Metric	“1”	“2”	“3”
Precision	1.000	1.000	1.000
Recall	1.000	1.000	1.000
F1 Score	1.000	1.00	1.000

Table 4.28 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of NB on Wine Data Set

The value of Matthews’s correlation coefficient (MCC) was found to be 1.000. It depicts a very strong positive relationship between the actual class labels and predicted class labels.

4.6.4 SVM Model on Wine Data Set

A machine learning model was created for SVM. The accuracy of the model was found to be 0.981. Furthermore, the confusion matrix is also depicted below.

Figure 4.35 Confusion Matrix of SVM on Wine Data Set

The precision, recall and f1 score for the class labels “1”, “2” and “3” are depicted below.

Metric	“1”	“2”	“3”
Precision	1.000	0.954	1.000
Recall	1.000	1.000	0.928
F1 Score	1.000	0.977	0.963

Table 4.29 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of SVM on Wine Data Set

The value of Matthews’s correlation coefficient (MCC) was found to be 0.972. It depicts a strong positive relationship between the actual class labels and predicted class labels.

4.6.5 ANN (MLP Classifier) Model on Wine Data Set

A machine learning model was created using Multi Layer Perceptron. The accuracy of the model was found to be 1.000. Furthermore, the confusion matrix is also depicted below.

Figure 4.36 Confusion Matrix of MLP Classifier on Wine Data Set

The precision, recall and f1 score for the class labels “1”, “2” and “3” are depicted below.

Metric	“1”	“2”	“3”
Precision	1.000	1.000	1.000
Recall	1.000	1.000	1.000
F1 Score	1.000	1.000	1.000

Table 4.30 Precision, Recall and F1 Score of MLP on Wine Data Set

The value of Matthews’s correlation coefficient (MCC) was found to be 1.000. It depicts a very strong positive relationship between the actual class labels and predicted class labels.

4.7 TRAINING TIME, PREDICTION TIME AND SPACE CONSUMPTION

Time in Seconds	Adult Data Set				
	CART	kNN	NB	SVM	ANN
Training Time	0.27362	2.73344	0.08479	43.56115	214.36294
Prediction Time	0.00342	0.01142	0.00230	0.00768	0.00534

Time in Seconds	Breast Cancer Data Set				
	CART	kNN	NB	SVM	ANN
Training Time	0.01159	0.00460	0.00891	0.01790	1.31209
Prediction Time	0.00260	0.00430	0.00221	0.00338	0.00309

Time in Seconds	Car Evaluation Data Set				
	CART	kNN	NB	SVM	ANN
Training Time	0.00688	0.00717	0.00932	0.15679	13.14594
Prediction Time	0.00258	0.00463	0.00234	0.00328	0.00248

Time in Seconds	Heart Disease Data Set				
	CART	kNN	NB	SVM	ANN
Training Time	0.00817	0.00655	0.00843	0.01759	0.53898
Prediction Time	0.00449	0.00427	0.00433	0.00539	0.00462

Time in Seconds	Iris Data Set				
	CART	kNN	NB	SVM	ANN
Training Time	0.00528	0.00317	0.00714	0.00973	0.49520
Prediction Time	0.00377	0.00391	0.00474	0.00250	0.00268

Time in Seconds	Wine Data Set				
	CART	kNN	NB	SVM	ANN
Training Time	0.00682	0.00430	0.00817	0.01200	2.20718
Prediction Time	0.00448	0.00539	0.00368	0.00518	0.00342

Table 4.31 Training Time and Prediction Time for Various Techniques

The implementation was done in Python 3.9 and the computer used for training and testing was running on intel i3 processor with 8GB of RAM and 128 GB SSD.

Data Set	Space Consumption in MB				
	CART	kNN	NB	SVM	ANN
Adult	2.6	4.3	1.5	3.2	4.0
Breast Cancer	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.4	5.3
Car Evaluation	0.2	0.1	0.1	2.5	5.5
Heart Disease	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.2	5.0
Iris	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.3	4.1
Wine	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.2	4.5

Table 4.32 Space Consumption of Various Techniques

4.8 SUMMARY OF THE RESULTS

This section gives the summary result of various classification techniques used in this study. This section also covers the pros and cons of each technique.

4.8.1 Summary on the Adult Data Set

Figure 4.37 Performance Analysis on Adult Data Set

On Adult data set, SVM, outperformed all other classification techniques in most of the performance metrics. ANN came second with kNN trailing behind. Naïve Bayesian classifier performed poorly in terms of F1-score and MCC in comparison to other classification technique.

4.8.2 Summary on the Breast Cancer Data Set

Figure 4.38 Performance Analysis on Breast Cancer Data Set

In Breast Cancer data set, ANN surpassed all other classification techniques in all of the performance metrics as shown in Figure 4.38. It was closely followed by SVM. The performance of other classification technique was also quite good with good values of MCC and F1 – score.

4.8.3 Summary on the Car Evaluation Data Set

Figure 4.39 Performance Analysis on Car Evaluation Data Set

In Car Evaluation data set, ANN surpassed all classification techniques over all of the performance metrics. ANN also showed high and consistent values of precision, recall and F1-score even for class with relatively fewer number of instances. The performance of other classifiers was not that best in terms of precision and recall. Naïve Bayesian classifier showed most poor values for MCC and accuracy in comparison to other classifiers.

4.8.4 Summary on the Heart Disease Data Set

Figure 4.40 Performance Analysis on Heart Disease Data Set

In heart disease data set, CART and Naïve Bayesian classifier worked best among other techniques which also were working decently. CART and Naïve Bayesian showed high precision and recall for both of the classes and ANN followed closely behind.

4.8.5 Summary on the Iris Data Set

Figure 4.41 Performance Analysis on Iris Data Set

The iris data set was balanced for all three classes and it consisted of 4 features. All of the data mining techniques worked off the charts for this data set resulting in very high accuracy, high value of precision, recall, f1-score and MCC. CART, kNN, SVM and ANN yielded 100 percent accuracy in the test set resulting in highest value for all other metrics.

4.8.6 Summary on the Wine Data Set

Figure 4.42 Performance Analysis on Wine Data Set

ANN surpassed all other classification technique in terms of all the metrics and Naïve Bayesian classifier also came head to head with ANN in this data set followed closely by CART. kNN had lowest values for across all the performance metric and hence worked poorly in this data set. ANN and Naïve Bayesian classifier also showed consistent value of f1-score for all the three classes and had highest value of MCC.

4.8.7 Summary of Training Time, Prediction Time and Space

Figure 4.43 Training Time and Prediction Time across different data sets

It is evident from the figure that ANN takes a huge amount of time for training time where the network learns the weight between the neurons. ANN are followed closely by SVM which is also very computationally expensive. Then comes kNN followed by CART. Naïve Bayesian classifier has the lowest time complexity among all the classifiers.

Figure 4.44 Space Consumed by Various Classifiers in Various Data Set

It is evident from figure 4.44 that, ANN and SVM consume more space but the space consumption doesn't grows too much as the function of number of instances of data. On the other hand, although kNN and CART seem to consume less space but when the number of instances increases (Adult Dataset), the space consumption increases sharply. Naïve Bayesian classifier consumed the least amount of memory among other classifiers.

5. CONCLUSION

In this thesis work, Decision Trees technique (CART), k Nearest Neighbors technique (kNN), Naïve Bayesian technique, Support Vector Machines technique (SVM) and Artificial Neural Networks technique (MLP) were used to build models for classification on the six data sets introduced in Chapter Three. Thereafter, the models built were analyzed on the basis of several metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, f1 score and Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC). This section will summarize the finding of the thesis.

Dataset Name	Variable types	Good Performance
Adult	Categorical, Integer	SVM
Breast Cancer	Real	All
Car Evaluation	Categorical	ANN
Heart Disease	Integer, Real	Naïve Bayes, CART
Iris	Real	All
Wine	Integer, Real	Naïve Bayes, ANN, SVM

Table 5.1 Best Performing Classifier on Various Data Sets

The Adult data set contained unequal number of instances for class labels so the accuracy and precision for class label “>50K” was lower than that of “<50k”. Support Vector Machines worked best for this data set in terms of all of the metrics. All the techniques performed well in the Breast Cancer data set because the data contained almost balanced number of instances for each class label. In this data set, Multi Layer Perceptron (ANN) surpassed all other techniques in most of the performance metrics.

In case of Car Evaluation data set the data set was imbalanced and comprised of categorical data mostly and even though some of the techniques were fairly accurate, they ended up with extremely poor values for precision and recall except Multi Layer Perceptron (ANN). MLP performed well and had high values of precision and recall even for the classes which contained relatively fewer numbers of instances. The Heart Disease data set was balanced and the data consists of continuous numeric values. CART and Naïve Bayes performed exceptionally well in Heart Disease data set. The Iris data set comprised of 4 attributes and was perfectly balanced with equal number of instances for each of the class labels. All the techniques performed exceptionally

well in the Iris data set. The Wine dataset consists of numeric attributes and the data set was mostly balanced. ANN, Naïve Bayes and SVM performed well in the Wine Data Set. Based on the results obtained from various forms of analysis conducted throughout the course of this thesis work, a general comparison of all the models is illustrated in the table 5.2 along with the advantages and limitations of each techniques.

Techniques	Advantages	Disadvantages
CART	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CART does not rely on data belonging to any particular type of distribution. • Not significantly affected by outliers in the data variables. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Small variation in the data set can result in different decision trees • Requires higher time to train the model.
kNN	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Classes does not need to be linearly seperable. • Well suitable for multi class classification 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time consuming to find the value of k in large data sets. • Memory limitation
Naïve Bayes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simple to implement. • High computa tional efficiency. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires large data set to obtain good results. • Conditional independence is assumed in class for rules.
SVM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High accuracy. • Works well even in non linearly seperable feature space. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High computational complexity and extensive memory requirements. • Slow.
MLP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easily applicable. • Can be applied to wide range of problems having different data distribution. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires high computation time if the network is large. • Difficult to figure out the number of neurons and hidden layers.

Table 5.2 Advantages and Disadvantages of Different Techniques.

6. FUTURE RECOMMENDATIONS AND LIMITATIONS

6.1 RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FUTURE WORK

Data is still being generated in vast swathes everyday and the volume of data being generated will only increase in the future. The data generated will be both of homegenous and heteregenous in nature with varying distribution. Thus the need to understand and unravel useful information from the data will also continue to rise. To effectively mine the data, a data scientist must have a good understanding of the data mining tasks, the data mining algorithms that can be employed and the hyper parameters of these algorithms. In this study, five data mining algorithms for classification were compared and analyzed over performance metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, f1 score and MCC. In the future, the analysis can be performed by taking data from newer fields such as data generated from IoTs .

One can also conduct a study on the choice of preprocessing techniques and the effect it has on the various performance metrics. Also, the effect of tuning various hyperparameters of data mining techniques on the various performance metrics can be experimented upon and studied to unravel how to pick the best value for these hyperparameters.

6.2 LIMITATIONS

More data sets can be analyzed to get more general picture but because of the time limitations, the data sets from other aspects of life such as image classification, natural language processing were not taken. Furthermore, data mining can be of several types. In this study we considered the different major data mining techniques used for classification. The idea can be expanded to figure out the best data mining techniques for other data mining tasks such as prediction, time- series analysis, association rule mining , clustering and summarization.

REFERENCES

- [1] Y. Fu, "Data mining. Tasks, techniques and applications.," *IEEE Potentials*, vol. 16, pp. 18–20, 1997.
- [2] P.-N. Tan, M. Steinbach, and V. Kumar, *Introduction to Data Mining*. 2016.
- [3] G. Kesavaraj and S. Sukumaran, "A Study On Classification Techniques in Data Mining," 2013.
- [4] S. Gorade, A. Deo, and P. Purohit, "A Study Some Data Mining Classification Techniques," *Int. J. Mod. Trends Eng. Res.*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 210–215, 2017, doi: 10.21884/ijmter.2017.4031.zt9tv.
- [5] S. S. Nikam *et al.*, "A survey on data mining classification algorithms," *Int. J. Mod. Trends Eng. Res.*, vol. 4, no. 6, pp. 1–6, 2013, doi: 10.1109/CSPC.2017.8305851.
- [6] S. Neelamegam and E. Ramaraj, "Classification algorithm in Data mining : An Overview," *Int. J. P2P Netw. Trends Technol.*, vol. 4, no. 8, pp. 369–374, 2013.
- [7] T. N. Phyu, "Survey of Classification Techniques," vol. I, pp. 33–95, 2009, doi: 10.1002/9781119439868.ch4.
- [8] K. Gibert, M. Sánchez-Marrè, and V. Codina, "Choosing the Right Data Mining Technique: Classification of Methods and Intelligent Recommendation," *Model. Environ. Sake Proc. 5th Bienn. Conf. Int. Environ. Model. Softw. Soc. iEMSS 2010*, vol. 3, pp. 2457–2464, 2010.
- [9] M. Kumari and S. Godara, "Comparative Study of Data Mining Classification Methods in Cardiovascular Disease Prediction," *Int. J. Comput. Sci. Trends Technol.*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 304–308, 2011, [Online]. Available: <http://www.ijcst.com/vol22/2/milan.pdf>.
- [10] A. H, Q. A., M. N., and E. M., "A Comparison Study Between Data Mining Tools over some Classification Methods," *Int. J. Adv. Comput. Sci. Appl.*, vol. 1, no. 3, 2011, doi: 10.14569/specialissue.2011.010304.
- [11] C. Shah and A. G. Jivani, "Comparison of data mining classification algorithms for breast cancer prediction," *2013 4th Int. Conf. Comput. Commun. Netw. Technol. ICCCNT 2013*, pp. 4–7, 2013, doi: 10.1109/ICCCNT.2013.6726477

- [12] M. Mustafa, S. F. Shazmeen, and M. R. Pawar, "Performance Evaluation of Different Data Mining Classification Algorithm and Predictive Analysis," *IOSR J. Comput. Eng.*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 1–6, 2013, doi: 10.9790/0661-1060106.
- [13] L. C. Borges, V. M. Marques, and J. Bernardino, "Comparison of Data Mining techniques and tools for data classification," doi: 10.1145/2494444.2494451.
- [14] S. Umadevi and K. S. J. Marseline, "A survey on data mining classification algorithms," *Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. Signal Process. Commun. ICSPC 2017*, vol. 2018-Janua, no. July, pp. 264–268, 2018, doi: 10.1109/CSPC.2017.8305851.
- [15] U. Fayyad, G. Piatetsky-Shapiro, and P. Smyth, "From Data Mining to Knowledge Discovery in Databases," *AI Magazine Volume 17 Number 3*. pp. 37–54, 1996, doi: 10.1142/7114.
- [16] B. Juba and H. S. Le, "Precision-Recall versus accuracy and the role of large data sets," *33rd AAAI Conf. Artif. Intell. AAAI 2019, 31st Innov. Appl. Artif. Intell. Conf. IAAI 2019 9th AAAI Symp. Educ. Adv. Artif. Intell. EAAI 2019*, pp. 4039–4048, 2019, doi: 10.1609/aaai.v33i01.33014039.
- [17] D. Chicco and G. Jurman, "The advantages of the Matthews correlation coefficient (MCC) over F1 score and accuracy in binary classification evaluation," *BMC Genomics*, vol. 21, no. 1, pp. 1–13, 2020, doi: 10.1186/s12864-019-6413-7.
- [18] D. Dua and G. Casey, "UCI Machine Learning Repository," 2021. <http://archive.ics.uci.edu/ml>.
- [19] "Adult Data Set," 2021. <https://archive.ics.uci.edu/ml/datasets/Adult>.
- [20] "Breast Cancer Wisconsin (Diagnostic) Data Set," 2021. <https://archive.ics.uci.edu/ml/datasets/Breast+Cancer+Wisconsin+%28Diagnostic%29>.
- [21] M. Bohanec, "Car Evaluation Data Set," 2021. <https://archive.ics.uci.edu/ml/datasets/Car+Evaluation>.
- [22] A. Janosi, W. Steinbrunn, M. Pfisterer, and R. Detrano, "Heart Disease Data Set," 1988. <https://archive.ics.uci.edu/ml/datasets/Heart+Disease>.
- [23] R. A. Fisher and M. Marshall, "Iris Data Set," 2021. <https://archive.ics.uci.edu/ml/datasets/Iris>.
- [24] M. et al Forina, "Wine Data Set." <https://archive.ics.uci.edu/ml/datasets/Wine>.
- [25] C. R. Harris, K. J. Millman, S. J. Van der Walt, and R. Gommers, "Array

- Programming with NumPy,” *Nature*, vol. 585, pp. 357–362, 2020, doi: 10.1038/s41586-020-2649-2.
- [26] E. Jones, T. Oliphant, and P. Peterson, “SciPy: Open Source Scientific Tools for Python,” 2001. <http://www.scipy.org>.
- [27] J. D. Hunter, “Matplotlib: A 2D graphics environment,” *Comput. Sci. Eng.*, vol. 9, pp. 90–95, 2007, doi: 10.1109/MCSE.2007.55.
- [28] M. L. Waskom, “seaborn: statistical data visualization,” *Open J.*, vol. 6, p. 3021, 2021, doi: 10.21105/joss.03021.
- [29] W. McKinney, “Data Structures for Statistical Computing in Python,” *Proc. 9th Python Sci. Conf.*, pp. 56–61, 2010.
- [30] F. Pedregosa, G. Varoquaux, and A. Gramfort, “Scikit-learn: Machine Learning in Python,” *J. Mach. Learn. Res.*, vol. 12, pp. 2825–2830, 2011.